

AMIGDALA

Alliance for Modelling Industries towards the Green Deal's objectives And circuLarity

D2.1 – Working procedure and data exchange tables for interaction between models, database, scenarios and dashboard.

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Note to the reader

This document finalises Work Package 2 on developing a soft-linked model suite for the proof-of-concept. It includes the working procedure to integrate the different AMIGDALA modules on data management, scenario building, integrated modelling, and decision analysis. It is an important milestone to pass, to define how all features of the concept work together in the AMIGDALA framework. In that way it also reports Milestone 4 'Scenarios, sectors and model/data-needs are defined'.

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AMIGDALA Project summary

Achieving climate neutrality by 2050, as envisioned in the European Green Deal, poses a multi-faceted challenge. Europe must foster a sustainable industrial sector that is not only climate-neutral but also globally competitive and resilient. This transformation requires strategic foresight to navigate the complex interplay of demand, global trade, and industrial production.

Decision-makers face critical choices, from crafting policies and regulations to investing in advanced technologies for public infrastructure and industrial assets. Supporting these decisions with actionable insights is essential to steering the evolution of the basic industry within the European Union.

The EU-funded AMIGDALA project aims to provide public and private decision-makers with insights from scenario analysis. The analysis is augmented by computer models to project transformation pathways towards climate neutral destinations. The scenarios are grounded in economic indicators and options to drive change that both policymakers and industry leaders can recognize and act upon.

To reduce the number of exogenous parameters, AMIGDALA is developing a modelling tool that integrates models from different domains. This integrated tool will link critical factors such as demand and trade, industrial production, energy and feedstock consumption, and climate effects. The data will span historical timelines from 1990 and make projections up to 2070, offering a comprehensive view of industrial transformation.

Additionally, the project will analyse local decision-making by industry clusters and utility operators. These insights will illuminate the practical implications of various pathways toward climate neutrality.

Public summary of this document

Europe is facing a big challenge — and a big opportunity. To reach its goal of becoming climate neutral by 2050, as outlined in the European Green Deal, industries across the continent need to become greener, more circular, and ready to compete in a changing global economy. But getting there is not simple. Success depends on smart decisions in a fast-moving world shaped by new technologies, shifting trade patterns, and evolving social and political demands.

That is where the AMIGDALA project comes in. Its mission is to help make sense of this complexity. AMIGDALA – short for Alliance for Modelling Industries towards the Green Deal’s objectives and Circularity – is building a powerful set of tools that can simulate possible futures for Europe’s industrial sector. These tools connect different types of models — covering the economy, energy use, materials, and climate — with real-world scenarios and input from stakeholders. The goal is to turn data and models into practical advice for the people making key decisions.

This document, Deliverable D2.1, is an important step forward. It shows how AMIGDALA’s models, data systems, storylines, and decision tools can work together. By proving that this kind of fully integrated system is technically possible, the project lays the foundation for delivering clear, useful insights to industry leaders and policymakers working to decarbonise Europe’s economy.

Executive summary of this document

To support the European Union's 2050 climate neutrality goals, the AMIGDALA project is developing an integrated modelling framework that guides industrial transformation in alignment with environmental and economic objectives. This deliverable, D2.1, establishes how different components, such as models, databases, scenarios, and decision-support tools, can interact in a structured, soft-linked framework. It is a pivotal milestone laying the conceptual and technical underpinnings to realise the AMIGDALA approach.

At the heart of the AMIGDALA framework lies a suite of nine interconnected modules, each developed by expert teams in scenario building, integrated modelling, data management, and decision analysis. These modules collaborate through a shared data repository, which ensures consistent and validated input for all models. Background and foreground scenarios feed into these models, which then generate raw outputs that are processed into metrics. These metrics help assess climate neutrality across five key dimensions: energy use, emissions, raw materials, production, and fossil carbon substitution in materials.

AMIGDALA's decision-support system incorporates diverse tools such as the Data Explorer, which visualizes both historical and projected data; the Decision Dashboard, which lets stakeholders explore outcomes based on their priorities; and the Decision Logic module, which uses Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) to rank scenarios based on user-defined key performance indicators.

Looking forward, the project will focus on scaling up the model suite, refining data exchange processes, expanding sectoral coverage, and validating outputs through stakeholder engagement. Deliverable D2.1 provides the foundational logic and infrastructure upon which subsequent modelling efforts and scenario analyses will build. It ensures that the AMIGDALA framework is ready to deliver meaningful insights to guide Europe's journey toward a climate-neutral, circular, and competitive industrial future.

Acronyms and abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
CBAM	Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism
ETS	Emission Trading System
EU	European Union
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MCDA	Multi Criteria Decision Analysis
MS	Member States
POC	Proof of Concept
ROW	Rest of World
SSP	Shared Socio-economic Pathway
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

Glossary

AMIGDALA CONCEPT	The combination of decision-making analysis with integrated multi-domain modelling for making projections.
AMIGDALA FRAMEWORK	Structure in which the modules of the AMIGDALA framework work together.
CONTEXT	Larger environment that puts a perspective on the themes
DATA EXPLORER	Module consisting of combination of data repository, a visualisation tool, as well as an API for the data to be retrieved.
DATA MANAGEMENT	Expertise on data management and technical data validation.
DATA REPOSITORY	Module consisting of all existing datasets: scenario and basic data already used by the models, historical data, and data output from models.
DECISION ANALYSIS	Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis based on decision-makers' preference for selected performance indicators
DECISION-MAKER	Roles in governmental and industry organizations that have a mandate to formalise and implement decisions.
DECISION SUPPORT DASHBOARD	Module consisting of the graphical user interface and interaction process for the application of the decision analysis logic.
INDICATORS	Set of 32 parameters that have been identified by interviewing public and private decision-makers as main drivers for their decisions, as reported in D1.1.
INTEGRATED MODELLING	Expertise to develop a consistent and converging integrated model suite to analyse energy, material and

INTEGRATED MODEL SUITE	climate system transitions and their impacts at global, EU and local level. Module consisting of a combination of models on economy and trade, feedstock and energy, circularity, and environment to analyse energy, material and climate system transitions and their impacts at global, EU and local level.
KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS	Sub-set of 10 indicators out of the 32 that were high graded for their relevance across government and industry.
MODULES	Distinct functional units that operate within the AMIGDALA framework.
PARAMETER	Piece of information identified in interviews
POLICY INSTRUMENTS	Regulatory Instruments ("command and control") Market-Based Instruments (e.g., taxes, subsidies, cap-and-trade) Information-Based Instruments (e.g., labelling, education).
SCENARIO BUILDING	Expertise focussed on scenario analysis, to develop consistent (foreground and background) scenarios and control levers on a global, EU and local level.
SCENARIO MODULE	Module consisting of combination of drivers, archetypes, and control levers.
THEME	Categories that group parameters into coherent subjects

Guidance notes for the document

The AMIGDALA **project** has brought partners together around the challenge to deliver modelling insights for advanced scenario projections in support of policy development and investment decisions required for a transformation to a sustainable European industry.

The AMIGDALA **concept** is the partnership's approach to address the challenge to develop advanced foresight through decision analysis and projections of what may be climate neutral, competitive, and resilient configurations of the energy intensive industries in Europe.

The AMIGDALA **framework** is the combination of modules in which the solutions that we develop materialise.

Current project phase

This document finalises Work Package 2 on developing a soft-linked integrated model suite for the proof-of-concept. It is an important milestone to pass because we need to prove that all features of the concept can work together in the AMIGDALA framework.

Next project phases

In Work Package 3 we will finalise the integrated model, decision framework and scenarios to reach technical completion. Work Package 4 is the deployment of the new modelling capacity to make projections of pathways to climate neutral destinations and analyse the pathways from the perspectives of different stakeholders.

Structure of this document

Chapter 1 introduces the project, provides grounding in the context and states the objectives. Chapter 2 establishes the conceptual AMIGDALA framework for integrating models, scenarios, and dashboard. Chapter 3 details the data requirements and outputs for each **module** (functional AMIGDALA unit). Chapter 4 examines the interconnections between these modules, focusing on their inputs and outputs. Similarly, chapter 5 outlines the interactions between **models** (analytical tools). Finally, chapter 6 concludes with a concise recap of the main findings, assessing the effectiveness of soft linking through data exchange tables.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project background

The European Green Deal sets ambitious climate goals, including a 55% reduction in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 2030, compared to 1990 levels, and climate neutrality by 2050. In 2022, industrial emissions accounted for 20.3% of total EU GHG emissions, underscoring the sector's critical role in meeting these targets (European Parliament 2024). Nevertheless, decarbonizing industry poses a significant challenge, for it must strike a delicate balance between environmental ambition and economic profitability and competitiveness.

Decarbonizing industry requires both technological solutions and policy intervention. Technological solutions fall into supply-side and demand-side approaches. Examples of supply-side solutions are energy efficiency improvements, electrification, and the deployment of low-carbon hydrogen as both a heat source and a chemical feedstock. Demand-side approaches, includes reducing material waste, substituting low-carbon alternatives for high-carbon inputs, and embracing circular economy (Rissman et al. 2020).

But technology alone is insufficient. A supportive policy framework is essential to drive technological adoption, promote circular practices, and ensure economic viability. Key interventions include carbon pricing mechanisms, with border adjustments to prevent carbon leakage, and strong governmental support for research, development, and deployment (Meckling, Sterner, and Wagner 2017).

Despite political willingness and the maturity of decarbonization technologies, the pathways to industrial decarbonization are clouded by uncertainty. The future low-carbon industrial landscape remains in flux: which technologies will prevail? How will trade patterns shift? Which demand side strategies will take root? Which policy interventions will foster the industrial sector's transformation? The answers remain elusive.

The Alliance for Modelling Industries towards the Green Deal's objectives and Circularity (AMIGDALA) sets out to pierce through the fog of uncertainty all around industrial decarbonization by equipping decision-makers, in government and industry, with the tools to define and evaluate viable pathways toward circular, climate-neutral, and competitive industries.

In AMIGDALA, we acknowledge that the complex interplay of technical, economic, social, and behavioural phenomena taking place in the European industrial transformation cannot be captured by one single model. Therefore, to achieve our goal, we champion an integrated modelling framework, encompassing multiple established models, each addressing a crucial dimension of the transition. This integrated framework comprises dedicated assessment models, such as TIAM-ECN and TIMES-Europe, a model of global trade, EXIOMOD, soil-based production, GLOBIOM, and circularity, CITS.

In addition, to ensure practical relevance, we align modelled projections with real-world decision-making practices by identifying key control levers and performance indicators for business and government. We call this alignment the decision-framework (D-framework), which serves as the foundation for scenario design. The designed scenarios provide input parameters for the models and serves as a bridge between internal model parameters with control levers and performance indicators that matter to users. Finally, to enhance the real-world impact of model outputs, we deploy an interactive online dashboard that allows users to explore projections from multiple perspectives and create personalized views.

Taken together, these methodological innovations enable decision-makers to navigate complex decarbonization pathways with clarity, steer toward a secure harbour by leveraging key control levers, and chart a course to a net-zero shore by translating insights into actionable strategies for industrial transformation.

1.2. Purpose of the document

A critical step in developing our integrated modelling approach lies in establishing the interaction between models, databases, scenarios, and dashboard - a key milestone in achieving AMIGDALA's goals.

This report details the data exchange framework devised for the proof-of-concept (PoC), demonstrating how we connect these components to create a coherent, functional system. By streamlining data integration, scenario development, and visualization, we ensure that our modelling framework delivers practical insights for stakeholders driving the industrial sector's transformation. Hence, it also reports Milestone 4 'Scenarios, sectors and model/data-needs are defined'.

This report does not cover the lessons learned from developing the PoC, for they will be addressed in the forthcoming deliverable, D2.2: “Lessons learned from the proof-of-concept”. It is worth noting that the data exchange framework presented herein may evolve based on insights gained during the POC’s execution.

1.3. WP2 on Model development & Proof-of-Concept of the integrated model and Decision Dashboard

This report is one of the key deliverables of Work package (WP) 2, “Model development and Proof-of-concept of the integrated model and D-framework”. WP2 aims to demonstrate how various components of the research approach, such as computational models, dashboards, and scenarios, can be seamlessly integrated to comprehensively analyse pathways towards industrial decarbonization. To achieve this goal, we contrived a proof-of-concept (PoC) to illustrate the feasibility and functionality of this integrated approach.

Although the scope of the AMIGDALA project is much broader, encompassing various energy-intensive industrial sectors, this proof-of-concept focuses only on the plastic industry and two scenarios for the sake of simplicity. This simplification allows us to focus on addressing the technical challenges associated with the soft linking of models. Soft linking refers to the practice of transferring data between models, datasets, or other components such that the output from one model serves as input to another, without creating direct interdependencies. In sharp contrast, a hard-linking approach directly integrates the models into a single, unified system, where the models share variables and operate as an interconnected whole. Hence, unlike a hard-linking approach, a soft-linking method enhances modularity and reusability, enabling seamless integration without altering the core model structure (Alikin, Erokhina, and Khorshev 2024).

The development of the PoC involves the following tasks:

- Collecting historical data.
- Developing a public data explorer.
- Developing a D-framework prototype.
- Defining scenarios.
- Integrating models.

These tasks will be detailed in a future deliverable.

2. Conceptual framework

2.1. AMIGDALA approach

The starting point of the GreenDeal transformation is today's situation of industrial production in Europe and import from global production to satisfy European demand and export. This situation today has severe climate impact, and we wish to move towards another situation that is climate neutral – which is what we call a 'destination'. Climate neutrality is the main objective set out by the GreenDeal and by the AMIGDALA project's Horizon Europe call. Competitiveness and Resilience are two other factors that should be weighed in the evaluation of feasibility of climate neutral destinations and pathways. The AMIGDALA project uses scenario analysis by computer modelling to identify climate-neutral destinations that have the lowest cost, as well as the lowest-cost pathways to reach them.

The key objective of this project is to identify pathways towards climate neutral European industry in 2050. As stated in the call and in AMIGDALA deliverable D1.1, *climate neutrality* is understood to have five dimensions: (1) industry's energy demand and use and energy efficiency, (2) industry's emissions including process emissions; (3) industry's use of raw materials, chemicals and water; (4) industry's production of consumer goods/equipment/construction products; (5) industry's possibility of replacing fossil carbon in materials by more sustainable streams.

It is to be expected that many destinations qualify as climate-neutral, while there are major differences between them. These differences may e.g. pertain to the availability of goods for European consumers, the dependence on trade relations and the distribution of production activities between European member states. These differences need to be articulated through analysis of the model projections, to provide the best possible view on the potential futures.

Attaining climate neutrality of industrial production requires coherent action in adjacent policy domains (e.g. emissions, energy, feedstock, products, agriculture) through the effective use of regulatory instruments (subsidies, mandates, pricing). These regulatory instruments are the key elements of the framework conditions, under which an optimal pathway will develop, starting from the current industrial activities in Europe.

Foreground scenarios of regulatory action in adjacent policy domains are to be developed against several background scenarios that describe circumstances on which the public and private actors in Europe have no influence. Each foreground scenario is the basis for a projection from today's situation to a climate-neutral destination.

Climate neutrality is a boundary condition for the model, which is implemented through programming the model to accept only climate-neutral end-states. Other characteristics of the destinations and pathways, such as 'competitiveness' and 'resilience' are to be assessed but will not be considered a target. Their levels will be assessed contextually and variably. Values may differ between pathways, depending on the specific context, underlying assumptions, or trade-offs involved.

To characterise pathways and destinations we use metrics as they appeal to different stakeholder groups, which we call 'indicators'. The indicators reflect the circumstances from the perspective of public and private decision-makers, as derived in a preliminary research work and reported in Deliverable 1.1 of the AMIGDALA project.

2.2. AMIGDALA concepts

To facilitate the alignment of the different parts that make up AMIGDALA, Table 1 summarises the main concepts that we have defined. These main concepts are to be used consistently throughout the project for clarity.

Table 1 AMIGDALA glossary of main concepts.

Concepts		Explanation	Remark
Indicators	Dimensions of climate neutrality	The 'five' dimensions of climate neutral industry ¹ .	Dimension #2 (industry's (process) emissions) is regarded as the leading dimension.
	For decision-making	The 32 indicators that decisionmakers use and identified by our preliminary research work ² .	10 'Key Performance Indicators' or 'KPI' were high graded as most relevant.
System characteristics	Competitiveness, resilience (and likely more).	These are complementary to climate neutrality and seem mutually exclusive. Within the project these are not seen as decision-making indicators.	We aim to develop a separate scoring for these aspects and where possible link these to the scenario definitions.
Policy areas		Examples of policy areas: energy, emissions, feedstock, circularity, products, trade.	Policy areas are controlled by <i>control levers</i> .
Control levers		Main public policy instruments to drive change and options for private decisionmakers to respond.	<u>Public</u> : subsidies, mandates, pricing. <u>Private</u> : investments, divestments.
Framework circumstances	Background scenario	A given for both public and private decision-makers.	Based on the Shared Socio-economic Pathways ³ and analysis of key drivers
	Foreground scenario	Circumstances defined primarily by the public regulatory instruments on key policy areas and the environment for private investment and divestment decisions.	Ideally the foreground scenarios define settings of the <i>control levers</i> , the settings of which are then parameterised for the models.
Destination		Configuration of industrial production in Europe, with European resource production and imports.	Climate neutrality of a configuration is a target that must be achieved.
Pathway		Trajectory of change from where we are today to a climate-neutral destination.	The AMIGDALA model suite will seek the lowest-cost pathway.
Decision logic		Characterising of pathways by weighting of indicators to rank the pathways through MCDA.	Used for ranking of scenario projections based on users' preferences.

Indicators are quantities to characterise the prevailing circumstances of the destination and on the pathway towards it. The ‘dimensions of climate neutrality’ reflect the five dimensions as outlined in the call. The indicators for ‘decision-making’ are the 32 indicators that have been defined by our own preliminary research and reflect the quantities that are considered important to most public and private decision-makers. Of those, 10 were high graded to Key Performance Indicators (KPI) as they have been mentioned in most of the interviews.

System characteristics refer to high-level concepts like e.g. climate neutrality, resilience and competitiveness that define the system as a whole. Although they can partially overlap, such as is the case for climate neutrality and competitiveness, they can also be partially excluding each other. Building the industry on the most competitive resources for instance would lead to strong dependencies on single sources and thus make the system less resilient. Likewise, climate neutrality may require making concessions on resilience and competitiveness and vice versa. Even though climate neutrality may need to be sacrificed to the benefit of other system interests, this project will maintain climate neutrality as an absolute objective. We will aim to develop a scoring for resilience and competitiveness that we can derive from the model results.

Policy areas are broad categories or domains in which governments or other policy-making bodies develop, implement, and evaluate policies. Each area encompasses a set of related issues, objectives, and instruments aimed at addressing specific societal challenges or goals. For AMIGDALA the most relevant are EU policy areas of the European Green Deal that directly affect the industry’s room to operate: energy, climate & emissions, water, chemicals & pollutants, waste, products & materials. The different regulations and directives under these policy areas address several different perspectives of the climate neutrality effort, as summarised and regularly updated by e.g. CircuLaw⁴.

Control levers are the means through which decisionmakers fulfil their mandates in line with the ambitions of their roles. Public decisionmakers have three main options to influence their economies:

¹ See section 2.1 of this report

² Section 3 of AMIGDALA Deliverable D1.1

³ "Climate Change 2021 - The Physical Science Basis" 13 August 2021.

⁴ https://www.circulaw.nl/European_green_deal.pdf

subsidies, mandates, and pricing. Subsidies stimulate desirable effects—from the consumption of sustainable goods and services to the investment in and operation of plants with lower climate impact. Subsidies are a way of socialising the cost, allowing society as a whole to bear the burden of striving for a particular cause. Pricing instruments, such as carbon taxes or emissions trading systems, are used to disadvantage economic pathways and products that are not desirable. They also generate income for public authorities, which can be recycled to support vulnerable groups or fund further transition efforts. The cost of pricing is borne by consumers and producers, and it sends a long-term signal that carbon-intensive practices will become increasingly uneconomic. Mandates are obligations to use—or refrain from using—selected feedstocks, technologies, or energy resources. They also include standards for products, such as energy performance requirements, recycled content quotas, or restrictions on high-emission goods.

In addition to these primary instruments, policymakers increasingly rely on information-based tools—such as carbon footprint labels, product transparency requirements, and green claims regulation—to support informed decision-making by consumers, investors, and firms. Public procurement is another underused but powerful lever, enabling governments to shape markets by demanding low-emission goods and services themselves.

Private decisionmakers, in turn, can respond to these signals in various ways. They may invest in products, production assets, or supply chains to remain or become competitive in the markets where they operate. Alternatively, they may divest from operations and sectors that are becoming economically or reputationally unsustainable. Beyond these financial decisions, firms increasingly act as value chain stewards, using their influence upstream and downstream to lower emissions they do not directly control. Many businesses are also shifting toward circular or service-based business models, which help decouple value creation from resource throughput. Climate-neutral positioning is no longer only a cost consideration but is becoming critical to managing reputation, access to capital, and long-term resilience.

Ultimately, no single instrument is sufficient. Effective governance of climate-neutral consumption requires carefully designed policy mixes, tailored to sectoral contexts and supported by strong public institutions, data infrastructures, and coordination mechanisms. Just

transition strategies are also essential to ensure fairness, legitimacy, and public support in the face of structural change.

Scenarios need to capture the most important control levers in their parameterization, while models need to be capable of capturing the effects of control levers on demand for products and investments.

Framework circumstances⁵ characterise the entire context for making policy and investment decisions. The scenarios should fully describe the environment for policymaking and business decisions at the beginning of a model run. These circumstances are first deemed to remain constant throughout the model run. As model integration progresses, we may allow for variable framework conditions that adapt to circumstances during a model run.

The **destination** is the lowest-cost outcome of a scenario that is climate neutral at a moment in the distant future. The outcome is described in terms of the installed production capacities within Europe for different technologies, the main flows of materials and energy, the supply from production and import, and demand from the consumers and export. While the ‘distant future’ in terms of years may be far away, the destination may only be one or two investment cycles away. This means that the next investment done needs to be just right, or capital is lost.

A **pathway** is the time-series of systems change from today’s framework circumstances and industrial production activity to the situation of the destination. Each scenario thus has its own unique destination and unique pathway of change. The model suite is set up to find the lowest-cost pathway from the starting point to the destination. Although the destination itself may be techno-economically feasible, it is necessary that the pathway towards it has acceptable risk. Characterising circumstances along a pathway may therefore be useful to decisionmakers to assess their risks and plan mitigation options.

The **decision logic** is the basis for the ranking of the scenario outcomes from a user’s perspective. It enables to evaluate pathways from the perspective of different decisionmakers through Multi Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA). The logic lets a user apply their own weights to indicators and apply their criteria to evaluate the desirability of ‘destinations’. Distinct user profiles may be pre-defined to make the

⁵ In the HEU call and project plan referred to as ‘Framework conditions’, here changed to ‘circumstances’ to distinguish from the AMIGDALA model ‘framework’.

differences visible and thus contribute to mutual understanding and trust, especially between public and private actors.

The modelling core of AMIGDALA

The core of the AMIGDALA concept is a modelling tool that includes technical, economic, and environmental domains. The domain models are to be linked to operate as if it were one model. This ‘pseudo-single’ model is provided with a starting point, boundary conditions and an objective to achieve, as visualised in Figure 1. The *starting point* represents the current system of e.g. demand, industrial production, energy generation and feedstock resources as well as setting of control levers to initiate change. The *destination zone* represents a climate neutral and lowest cost end-point of the transformation in 2050, which is the target to be achieved. The optimal *pathway* connects the starting point to the destination zone with the lowest cost. The destination as well as the pathway are described in terms of indicators. The *framework circumstances* are the conditions and boundaries for the model to find solutions for the pathway. The objective is to move from the starting point to the destination against the lowest cost / highest Net Present Value.

Figure 1 Visualisation of the core of the AMIGDALA concept.

Functions surrounding the modelling core

The modelling core is surrounded by functions to provide initial conditions, boundary conditions and process the output, shown in Figure 2. The basic data provide the current make-up of the global energy system, the basic industrial infrastructure in Europe and techno-economic information about relevant technologies of high TRL

that can be deployed in supply chains. The control levers and other conditions together provide the boundary conditions for the model to find acceptable solutions. The output of a model run, with full information about the destination and pathway is the basis from which indicators are derived and, with the addition of user preferences, the decision logic is applied.

Figure 2 Visualisation of functions surrounding the AMIGDALA modelling core.

The AMIGDALA concepts outlined above are implemented through functions that are executed in sequence and exchange data between them. The functions are packaged in ‘modules’ that are produced by the expertise teams.

2.3. AMIGDALA modules and workflow

The AMIGDALA framework⁶ it is made up by nine modules, as visualised in Figure 3. The modules each have a well-defined function within the framework and are built by one of the four expertise groups, shown in distinct colours.

Knowledge and skills in the AMIGDALA project are concentrated in four specialized expertise groups: Scenario building, Integrated modelling, Data management and Decision analysis. Each group consists of one lead-partner and has members of the other partners to include their expertise on the topic and liaise with the other expertise groups that develop other modules. The nine modules are produced by the four

⁶ See: AMIGDALA Deliverable 1.1

expertise groups. The exchange of information between the modules needs to be coordinated. The coordination is managed by the liaisons in the expertise groups that develop the modules.

Figure 3 Modules in the AMIGDALA framework, with arrows indicating the flow of information. The Data-explorer, Narratives of destination and pathways and the Decision dashboard are interfaces with the public.

Some modules are directly involved in making projections (background & foreground scenarios and modelling). Other modules can be seen as providing a service towards the model (data repository) or the users (historic data & data explorer, decision-logic & decision-dashboard). The purpose and functionality of the modules is described below:

Module - Integrated model suite

The integrated model suite makes the projections towards the future, through solving as-one a set of models in different domains. The domains cover demand for products and trade, global energy generation, circularity and recycling technologies, soil-based production of renewable feedstock and industrial production from circular and renewable feedstock. Within the model suite, the models are linked through their outputs and inputs, and the models share the same harmonized basic data. All model solvers are steered by the same boundary conditions and final objectives that are determined through

the parameterization of the scenarios. The model suite needs to optimize its operation and respect the spatial and temporal frames and computational constraints of the domain models. Main result is optimal pathways to reach certain policy goals.

The Integrated model suite takes basic data and scenario parameters from the Data repository. The integrated model outputs raw datasets for post-processing.

Module - Background & foreground scenarios and narratives

Scenario studies distinguish between different futures that may arise based on the analysis of uncertainties. Background scenarios reflect those circumstances that cannot be influenced by any of the public or private stakeholders. These circumstances are a given. The foreground scenarios reflect the options that decisionmakers have to influence their own destiny through their mandates and means, within a selected background scenario. A foreground scenario is where the 'Control levers' are set through which policy is turned into in regulatory action. The primary public levers to drive change in policy areas are *subsidies*, *mandates*, and *pricing*. The main private levers to respond are to *invest* in production means or *divest* from producing assets.

The scenarios are narratives that describe a particular future that ensues from uncertainty analysis and reasoning. AMIGDALA will build on existing scenarios as much as the objectives allow. Especially the foreground scenarios need to be tailored towards describing the rationale to use control levers in policy areas.

These narratives need to be parametrised to become numerical input for the model suite. Especially the parameterization of scenarios for the model suite needs the attention of the scenario team.

This module produces as output a set of scenarios. Each scenario is accompanied by a narrative that captures its essence and circumstances that may cause it to arise, and a set of parameters through the Data repository that is input to the model suite.

Module - Post-processing of raw model output

Each model in the model suite produces output in data files. These data files hold all information that is characteristic of each model domain. These raw data are converted through post-processing (e.g. selection, aggregation, and visualization) into a set of indicators that are useful to analysts, policy makers and other stakeholders. The post-processing

thus delivers the indicators (primary, secondary, tertiary) as they are made available to model users in a way that is meaningful to them.

Post-processing receives raw model output data and derives the sets of indicators. These sets are validated for consistency and made available for publication through the Data explorer and the Decision dashboard.

Module - Destination and pathway narratives

The scenario narratives reflect the logic of actions by different decisionmakers within defined circumstances. The destination and pathway narratives describe the projected outcome in words and aim to find relations of cause and effect between the scenario and the outcome. The destination narratives discuss the status in the projected final year and evaluate it from different viewpoints. The indicators and how they are interpreted and perceived by the different stakeholder groups (e.g. departments of public governance, member states, operating assets, business units and global ultimate owners) can be discussed to explain how the initial choices of the scenario led to the outcomes.

Destination and Pathway narratives receives a set of indicators for each scenario. In this narrative the causal relation is explored with the settings of the Control levers in the scenario. It can be accessed by the Data explorer and is part of the public interface.

Module - Data repository

The repository holds the historic data of the five dimensions, the parameters sets from the scenario analyses and the raw model outputs with derived performance indicators.

Particularly important for the models is that that should use the same harmonized and validated basic data. Otherwise, the models may produce 'inaccurate' or unrepresentative optimum pathway and destination. Therefore, the data repository module serves to facilitate this harmonization and validation of technology characterisations used by the models. The data structure of each of the models should remain leading so as not to interfere with the model operation. It may be foreseen that a central repository is created from aggregating the data in all separate models and publishing updates towards the model input files after harmonization between them and validation with experts, sectors, and the JRC.

The data repository receives data-files from the models and combines these into a central repository. The data is validated and where

necessary updated. Before technical completion, a new version of each model's input file is derived from the validated and harmonized data repository.

Module - Historic data on five dimensions of climate neutrality

Climate neutrality is the central objective of the 'Green Deal' industry transition, to revert the climate impact that is happening today. The five dimensions on which the energy intensive industry has climate impact today have been specified in the HEU call as:

- (1) industry's energy demand and use and energy efficiency,
- (2) industry's emissions including process emissions;
- (3) industry's use of raw materials, chemicals and water;
- (4) industry's production of consumer goods/equipment/construction products;
- (5) industry's possibility of replacing fossil carbon in materials by more sustainable streams.

The contribution of this module is to have a measure of these dimensions (where possible) that can be derived from public historic data on industrial impact. The historic trending on these dimensions is to be extended with the model projections, wherever that is possible to derive the measure by post-processing the raw model output. The dimensions of climate neutrality derived from historic data as well as from raw model output can be browsed through the data explorer.

The historic data module defines, where feasible, how to compose the numerical values for each of the five dimensions from public historic data of statistics offices and stored in the repository.

Module - Data explorer (facing the public)

The data explorer will enable to browse the AMIGDALA scenarios and model output in a structured way. To enhance the accessibility for a larger audience, the data explorer needs to have an intuitive interface that lets a user find and arrange model output and corresponding input parameters for different scenarios. The data explorer can visualise the historic trending of the five dimensions and extrapolate it through to the projections made by AMIGDALA.

The data explorer can publish validated sets of output data for scenarios.

Module - Decision logic

Actors within industry and government both have their specific roles & ambitions as well as mandates & means to achieve their goals. In preliminary research, we have established a set of ten *Key Performance Indicators*⁷ (KPI) that represent how most actors view their space for decision-making. There are some indicators that most stakeholders use, and some that are more important from a public position and others more from a private or industry position. The decision logic lets individual users rank the outcome of scenarios projections from their point of view. The decision logic uses Multi Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) to apply weight factors to KPIs and make a preference. The MCDA thus allows to rank all scenarios with their outcomes from different points of view.

The decision logic module takes the value of the KPIs from all available scenario outcomes from the Data repository and the weight factors that are set by the user of the Decision dashboard as input. The output of the module is the ranking number of the scenarios for the given weight factors.

Module - Decision dashboard (facing the public)

The decision dashboard is the interface where the user indicates the preferred weighting of the indicators used in the decision logic, as well as the display of the scenario ranking that follows from the MCDA. This will enable a public user to identify the scenario that best fits with the preferences of their perspective.

In the interface, relative weights can be assigned for the ten Key Performance Indicators. The setting interface and algorithm need to ensure that the KPIs are comparable, so all inputs are normalized.

The Decision dashboard shows a list of scenario projections. The list is ranked by the MCDA score. Each line shows all the ten Key Performance Indicators. The Decision dashboard module receives its input from the Decision logic module. The module receives as input the ranking of the scenarios. The module shows a ranked list of the scenarios and secondary & ternary indicators. The initial ranking is according to the

⁷ See deliverable 1.1, paragraph 3.2.3.

weight factors. The ranking may be changed by selecting a ranking the indicators.

Workflow

Preparatory work makes the basic data available, identifies background and foreground scenarios within those. The scenarios are parameterised. As we expect progressing insight and errata, version control is required of the model, the sets of basic data, and scenario parameters.

Each parameter-set is run through the model to produce as many sets as possible of output data. The sets of output data are post-processed to derive the primary, secondary and tertiary indicators for each scenario. See Figure 4.

The sets of scenario and output in terms of indicators and possibly other data is validated before releasing for publication through the web-interface of the Decision dashboard and the Data explorer.

Figure 4. Workflow

3. Key inputs and outputs of the 9 modules

This chapter focuses on the nine modules, including the integrated model suite, without going into the details of each individual model. It provides an account of the **key data requirements (inputs)** and **outputs** associated with each module.

The next chapter (Chapter 4) describes how the modules are linked through selected inputs and outputs from the full list collected in this chapter. Not all data are necessarily exchanged between modules.

3.1. Data repository

The data repository serves as the centralized storage for all relevant datasets used in the project, ensuring that data from models, scenarios, and other sources are easily accessible and meticulously organized. Data will be harmonized and standardized to align with the repository's structure, including consistent terminology, as well as geographical and temporal resolutions, ensuring compatibility and coherence across the entire data ecosystem.

Concretely, the data repository is being set by IIASA, or to be more precise, part of the data explorer described below. For this, IIASA's own and established infrastructure will be used, described in detail on their website.⁸

The repository's architecture is designed to ensure scalability, allowing it to accommodate increasing volumes of data as the project progresses. This is crucial for maintaining long-term data accessibility and ensuring smooth operations over time.

An essential component of the data repository is the data required for the models to function. This mainly concerns data used by multiple models; data which is only required by one model will not be stored in data repository for the PoC. Input data is specific to a model run and can be provided by the scenario expertise, another model, or can be any other data that needs to be harmonized between at least 2 models. To make sure that the data used and being provided matches a specific scenario or model run, all data will be stored with its corresponding metadata.

⁸ <https://github.com/iamconsortium/common-definitions>

Before setting up the data explorer, a list of variables for the historical and model data, as well as the regions for the PoC will be proposed by DECHEMA with amendments from the model owners according to each model's needs.

Moreover, user management will also be part of this initial setup, to enable the upload of historic data and results from the model runs.

Table 2: Inputs and outputs of Module Data explorer

	Module Data repository
Inputs & data requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> List of variables and regions which need to be included in the data explorer for visualisation. User access management
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to the data explorer Ability to upload data to the data explorer

3.2. Historic data of the 5 dimensions

Historical data from 1990 until today will be integrated in the data explorer. The integration process involves importing datasets from various publicly available sources, including government agencies, research institutions, industry associations and open data platforms. As the data will come from various sources, they need to be harmonized and standardized to fit the repository's structure.

Historical data will serve as references for the model outputs, as both will be displayed together. This combination of both past evolution and future projection provides valuable insights into trends, but also helps in calibrating the models, making the produced data more robust.

For the proof-of-concept industry, historical data for the EU and its member states will be collected from Eurostat, Plastics Europe, Petrochemicals Europe, and others. Table 3 displays it for the five dimensions of climate neutrality.

Table 3. List of collected historical data for the PoC along the five dimensions of climate neutrality. The data will be aligned with model output data. For the models' point of view on the five dimensions, reference is made to Table 11.

<u>Dimension</u>	<u>Historic data</u>	<u>Unit</u>	<u>Source</u>	<u>Geographical scope</u>	<u>Time scope</u>
(1) energy demand and use and energy efficiency <i>Process oriented</i>	Final energy consumption in industry: - non-energy use; - energy use; - specific to chemicals and petrochemicals. Primary energy consumption	ktoe	Eurostat	EU27 MS	1990-2023
(2) emissions including process emissions <i>Process + also scope 3 up- and downstream = life cycle</i>	GHG Emissions Processes	Mt CO2eq/yr	EDGAR database	208 countries	1990-2023
	GHG Emissions from petrochemicals and carbon black production	kt CO2eq/yr	Eurostat	EU27 MS	1990-2023
	CO2 price ETS 1	US\$/tCO2	World Bank	EU	2005-2024
(3) use of raw materials, chemicals, and water <i>Material input focus</i>	"Fossil energy materials/carriers": - direct material input, - imports, - material use, - exports	kt/year	Eurostat	EU27 MS	2010-2023
(4) production of consumer goods / equipment / construction products <i>Downstream Product manufacturing, including all circular R-strategies</i>	Production value of plastic products, rubber products	M€/year	Eurostat	EU27 MS	2005-2020
(5) possibility of replacing fossil carbon in materials by more sustainable streams	- Feedstock consumption for steam cracking - Production and consumption of ethylene, propylene, and benzene.	kt/year	Petrochemicals Europe	EU-15 aggregated	1990-2023
Renewable / circular feedstock - focus on carbon	"Circular material use rate" (Eurostat indicator over all materials)	%	Eurostat	EU27 MS	2010-2023

Table 4: Inputs and outputs of Modules Data repository – Historic data

	Module Historic data
Inputs & data requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • none
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collected data, to be uploaded to the data explorer

3.3. Data explorer

Whereas the data repository is merely a storage hub for the data used and generated by the models, the data explorer provides an interface that empowers users to retrieve and visualise the data stored in the repository.

Therefore, the data explorer serves as an intuitive and interactive interface to query and retrieve datasets from the repository. It will include advanced search functionalities, enabling users to filter data by e.g. dimensions of climate neutrality, keywords, dates, specific model types and model runs.

The data explorer used in this project is part of IIASAs Scenario Services, which is an established data hub in the modelling community for more than a decade. It includes a visualization tool through charts or tables and ensures that users from different teams, including modelers, scenario planners, and dashboard developers, can easily access the data they need.

The data explorer is accessible via a secure web-based platform. As such, an application programming interface (API) will be available to allow connections to the Decision Dashboard, among others.

Access controls and user permissions are implemented to safeguard sensitive data while allowing appropriate stakeholders to view and manipulate the data they require. This service will be managed directly by the IIASA-ECE permission management system.

Table 5: Inputs and outputs of Module Data explorer

	Module Data Explorer
Inputs & data requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historic data
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graphical visualization of historic data on five dimensions

3.4. Background and foreground scenarios and narratives

The transformation of the European industry towards climate neutrality is shaped by a dynamic interplay of external forces and policy decisions. *Background scenarios* describe exogenous, large-scale trends, such as global economic shifts, technological advancements, geopolitical developments, and environmental constraints, which set the broader context wherein industry operates. These scenarios help in delineating external conditions beyond the direct influence of European policymakers and industry stakeholders.

Foreground scenarios, in contrast, focus on decisions that drive change—policy actions, investments, and technological shifts—that stakeholders can influence. These scenarios show how different rules, economic changes, and technologies shape industrial change and the move toward climate neutrality. Foreground scenarios always build upon a specific background, comprising a combination of underlying contexts and a set of actionable options.

Background and foreground scenarios do not exist independently. The graph illustrates how different foreground scenarios (A or B) are combined with background scenarios (A or B) to form distinct scenarios. Each foreground scenario includes specific actionable options, demonstrating the interplay between background contexts and strategic choices.

Figure 5: Graphical overview of scenario definitions.

A *baseline scenario* establishes a reference case for comparison with alternative pathways and comprises background and foreground elements. It serves as a benchmark to measure the impact of policy interventions on investment decisions, technological adoption, and emission reductions in the industrial sector.

In AMIGDALA, the process of building scenarios is deeply rooted in academic literature, policy reports, and stakeholder insights. This approach ensures that the scenarios are both theoretical sound and relevant. The process is driven by following inputs:

1. EXISTING SCENARIO FRAMEWORKS:

AMIGDALA leverages well-established scenario frameworks to ensure consistency and comparability with global and regional foresight studies. These include:

- Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs): SSPs provide comprehensive narratives on global socio-economic developments, climate policy challenges, and adaptive capacities. AMIGDALA extends the SSP framework to focus specifically on the transformation of European energy-intensive industries (Bauer et al. 2017; O'Neill et al. 2014).
- EU Impact Assessments: Insights from the European Commission's impact assessments, such as those for the 2040 emissions target, provide regulatory context and strategic benchmarks, ensuring alignment with European Green Deal objectives.
- Industrial Foresight Studies: Sector-specific foresight studies, including those on hydrogen infrastructure, carbon capture, and circular economy models, inform detailed scenario narratives, particularly for high-emission sectors such as cement, steel, chemicals, and non-ferrous metals.

2. STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT AND PROPOSED KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS:

AMIGDALA places a strong emphasis on stakeholder-driven scenario building to enhance relevance and actionable insights. This is achieved through:

- Consultations and workshops: Direct engagements with policymakers, industry leaders, and research institutions identify critical drivers, control levers, and key performance indicators. This collaborative approach ensures that scenarios reflect realistic and actionable strategic choices.

- Decision-maker preferences analysis: In-depth interviews and feedback sessions in Deliverable D1.1 captured decision-makers' perspectives on economic performance indicators and regulatory uncertainty. This approach ensures that scenario parameters are aligned with stakeholders' decision contexts.
- Community of practice: An iterative feedback mechanism is embedded within the project, facilitating continuous refinement of scenario narratives and ensuring alignment with evolving stakeholder needs.

3. ESTIMATIONS OF UNCERTAINTIES FOR THE FUTURE: Uncertainty is an inherent aspect of long-term scenario analysis. Background scenarios are defined by factors that introduce uncertainty in the transition of the EU industry. AMIGDALA addresses this by:

- Quantitative and Qualitative Uncertainty Analysis: Scenarios are developed to capture a range of plausible futures, incorporating uncertainties in technological developments, policy interventions, and market dynamics.
- Scenario Archetypes and Contrasting Pathways: AMIGDALA employs a set of contrasting scenario archetypes, including high and low technology adoption rates, stringent versus lenient regulatory frameworks, and the degree of international interaction, competition, and collaboration among countries on issues such as trade, energy supply, and environmental policies. These archetypes help to identify risks, opportunities, and trade-offs associated with various pathways, providing decision-makers with actionable insights.
- Sensitivity analysis: Foreground scenarios undergo rigorous sensitivity analysis to assess the impact of key uncertainties on transformation pathways. Additionally, outputs are benchmarked against other relevant scenario studies to ensure credibility and robustness.

4. HISTORICAL DATA: to ground the scenarios in robust evidence, AMIGDALA integrates:

- Historical trends and macroeconomic indicators: Detailed data on historical energy consumption, industrial production, trade patterns, and socio-economic indicators are gleaned from trusted databases, including Eurostat and IEA.

5. SCENARIO ASSUMPTIONS ON POTENTIAL EVOLUTIONS OF KEY TRENDS: these assumptions provide a comprehensive framework for

exploring potential evolutions of key trends shaping the future of European industries, such as demand dynamics, trade patterns, and evolving consumer preferences.

- **Sectoral projections:** Sectoral projections are driven by demand dynamics, trade patterns, and evolving consumer preferences. These projections assess how different sectors within the European industrial landscape will grow, transform, and compete under varying scenarios of economic development and regulatory environments.
- **Technological pathways:** Technological pathways outline the evolution of industrial technologies, focusing on decarbonization, digitalization, and circularity. These pathways are informed by technological learning curves, R&D investments, and innovation diffusion. Scenarios may include expected technological advancements based on historical trends and current developments, without assuming any breakthrough innovations or accelerated adoption. This includes:
 - **Incremental Efficiency Improvements:** Gradual improvements in energy efficiency, process optimization, and material efficiency in existing industrial processes, driven by market dynamics and cost competitiveness.
 - **Technology Diffusion Rates:** Adoption rates of currently available low-carbon technologies, such as electrification of industrial processes, energy recovery systems, and incremental efficiency upgrades, reflecting historical diffusion patterns.
 - **Cost and Performance Trends:** Projections of cost reductions and performance improvements in established technologies, informed by learning curves and economies of scale.
 - **Digitalization and Automation:** Continued integration of digital technologies (e.g., IoT, AI, and advanced automation) for process optimization, productivity gains, and energy management, based on current industry trends.

6. CURRENT POLICY TRENDS: Scenarios incorporate existing and planned EU policies relevant to industrial decarbonization, reflecting the regulatory landscape as it stands today. This includes:

- **EU Climate and Energy Frameworks:** Current targets and regulations, such as the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS),

Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), and sector-specific emission reduction goals.

- Industrial policies to reach climate neutrality: Policies promoting energy efficiency, renewable energy integration, and circular economy practices within energy-intensive sectors such as chemicals, cement, steel, and non-ferrous metals.
- Planned Policy Trajectories: Announced but not yet implemented policies, ensuring that the baseline reflects foreseeable regulatory changes.
- Policy Interactions and Spillovers: Consideration of interactions between national and EU-wide policies, including potential trade impacts and competitive dynamics within the European Economic Area (EEA).

7. ECONOMIC AND DEMOGRAPHIC ASSUMPTIONS

- Macroeconomic Growth Assumptions: Projections of GDP growth, population dynamics, and urbanization trends, based on reputable sources such as Eurostat, the International Monetary Fund (IMF), and the Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs).

8. MARKET AND RESOURCE DYNAMICS

- Global Competition: Assumptions on international trade flows, import dependencies, and the competitive positioning of European industries, considering global supply chains and geopolitical influences.
- Level of Circularity: Current rates of material use, waste generation, and recycling practices, aligned with existing circular economy strategies but without assuming radical shifts towards full circularity.

Table 6. Overview of the elements considered in the design of both background and foreground scenarios.

	<i>BACKGROUND</i>	<i>FOREGROUND</i>
EXISTING SCENARIO FRAMEWORKS:	X	
STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT AND PROPOSED KPIS	X	
ESTIMATIONS OF UNCERTAINTIES FOR THE FUTURE:		X
HISTORICAL DATA	X	X
SCENARIO ASSUMPTIONS ON POTENTIAL EVOLUTIONS OF KEY TRENDS	X	
CURRENT POLICY TRENDS		X
ECONOMIC TRENDS AND DEMOGRAPHICS	X	
MARKET AND RESOURCE DYNAMICS		X

Table 6 provides an overview of what elements are considered in the development of both background and foreground scenarios.

To model these scenarios, they must be translated into variables, developed in collaboration with the data expertise team, which can be used directly or indirectly by the models. Also, the AMIGDALA framework translates this quantitative and qualitative information into compelling narratives that illuminate decision making. These narratives paint a picture of how industrial landscapes evolve under different policy choices and market conditions, highlighting key turning points where opportunities arise, or risks escalate. By identifying these critical junctures, stakeholders can anticipate challenges, seize strategic advantages, and create alternative pathways towards industrial transformation.

The key outputs of this module include carefully crafted scenarios that delineate the system's boundary conditions and deliver internally consistent datasets. These scenarios are designed to reflect realistic and actionable control options for both government and industry stakeholders. Additionally, this module delivers a baseline scenario that seamlessly integrates elements from both background and foreground scenarios, such as global economic trends, technological developments, and geopolitical influences, while incorporating strategic decisions modelled in the foreground scenarios.

Overall, the scenarios module provides the contextual boundaries for the optimization models within the integrated model suite, influencing both input parameters and output interpretation. The scenarios developed in this module comprise drivers and control levers. Drivers are external influences such as policy changes, market dynamics, and technological advancements. Control levers are the decision-making tools available to policymakers and industry leaders, such as subsidies and investment decisions on production capacity.

Table 7 provides an overview of the inputs, data requirements, and outputs for this module.

Table 7: Inputs and outputs of Module Background and foreground scenarios and narratives

	Module Background and foreground scenarios and narratives
Inputs & data requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder needs • Proposed KPIs • Uncertainties for the future • 'External' or 'contextual' drivers • Control levers (direct drivers) • Historical data • Potential evolutions of key data related to the scenarios, such as product demands and GDP.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foreground scenarios for the full model suite by combining backgrounds & a set of control levers, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Internally consistent datasets related to scenario definition ○ Boundary conditions. • A baseline scenario that includes background and foreground elements.

3.5. Integrated model suite

The integrated model suite uses internally consistent scenario input parameters as basis for its projections.

The exact subset of scenario parameters used, will differ between the models, depending on the geographical scope and the domains included in each model. For the global models the background scenarios will be most relevant. These large-scale, exogenous trends are

important in setting the global context in the model suite, as they will impact production, availability of and demand for products and energy (commodities) as well as associated costs in the different global regions. On European level, next to the global context, the actionable elements of the foreground scenarios, e.g. policies and (assumed) targets on carbon neutrality, circularity, and competitiveness as well as (strategic) technological preferences, will greatly impact the industrial pathways to sustainability.

For a given set of scenario parameters, a full run/optimization of the integrated model suite results in a large collection of output parameters related to energy, economy, materials, circularity and GHG emissions. Together they describe the evolution of the economy, the energy system, and particularly, the industry. As such the output parameters define the industrial pathways to sustainability, which will be captured in selected indicators for clarity (see below).

For each of the models, inputs needed from scenario and/or model(s) have been defined in an Excel file named "[Model data input requirements overview.xlsx](#)". The scenario input for each model is presented in Table 8. Here, the different scenario inputs are defined for each model in terms of sector, service / energy or material demand and unit. But also, it is specified what the driver of the parameter is and the geographical resolution (the years and the time resolution are not presented here for reasons of readability). Table 8 clearly shows that the global models, which are executed first, require extensive scenario input however, this input is provided at a global resolution, consistent with the scope of the global scenarios. In general, the EU models need less scenario input since input is coming from other, global models (see the chapter on Data exchange between models). The local models need even less scenario input since most of the inputs stem from EU models.

Table 8. Overview of scenario input for each of the models in the AMIGDALA model suite.

St	Model	Demand / supply	Service / energy / material demand or other	Unit	Driver in AMIGDALA	Coming fr	Geographical resolution
1	TIAM-ECN	Agriculture	Agriculture (AGR)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Residential	Residential cooling (RC1)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Residential	Residential appliances (REA)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Residential	Residential space heating (RH1)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Residential	Residential hot water (RHW)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Residential	Residential cooking (RK1)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Residential	Residential other (ROT)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Commercial	Commercial cooling (CC1)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Commercial	Commercial Cooking (CCK)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Commercial	Commercial space heating (CH1)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Commercial	Commercial hot water (CHW)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Commercial	Commercial office equipment (COE)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Commercial	Commercial other (COT)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Transport	Transport buses (TRB)	Bv-km	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Transport	Transport cars (TRC)	Bv-km	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Transport	Transport small vehicles (TRSV)	Bv-km	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Transport	Transport trucks (TRT)	Bv-km	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Transport	Transport rail freight (TRF)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Transport	Transport rail passenger (TRP)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Transport	Domestic navigation (TWD)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Transport	International navigation (TWI)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Transport	Domestic aviation (TAD)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Transport	International aviation (TAI)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Industry	Chemicals (ICH)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Industry	Iron and Steel (IIS)	Mt	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Industry	Pulp and paper (ILP)	Mt	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Industry	Non-ferrous metals (INF)	Mt	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Industry	Non metals (INM)	Mt	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Industry	Other industry (IOI)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Industry	Industrial and other non energy uses (NEO)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Industry	Lubricants (Transport) (NEU)	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN	Industry	Other non-specified industrial consumption (ON	PJ	Regional GDP/Population	Scenario	37 world regions
1	TIAM-ECN		CO2 and energy policies			Scenario	37 world regions
2	EXIOMOD	All sectors	Capital and labor productivity	mIn euro	GDP	Scenario	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD		Population	mIn	POP	Scenario	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD		Transfers from gov to hh	mIn	POP	Scenario	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD		Economic policies			Scenario	7 world regions + EU MS
3	GLOBIOM		Population	mIn	POP	Scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
3	GLOBIOM		Land use policies			Scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
3	GLOBIOM		SDG targets			Scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
3	GLOBIOM		Trade costs / policies			Scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
3	GLOBIOM		Technical progress			Scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
4	CITS		Population	mIn	Projection	Scenario	EU MS
4	CITS		Plastic polymer composition			Scenario	EU MS
4	CITS		Circular R-policies			Scenario	EU MS
5	PRISM		Recycling policies			Scenario	EU MS
5	PRISM		Technological learning curves	CAPEX & efficiencies per tonne capacity		Scenario	
6	TIMES-Europe	Residential	Housing: detached/semi-detached/flat	1000 houses	MS POP	Scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Commercial	Street Lighting	1000 units	MS POP	Scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Transport	Passenger Transport - Car	Bpkm	MS POP	Scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Transport	Passenger Transport – Motorized two-wheeler	Bpkm	MS POP	Scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Transport	Passenger Transport - Bus	Bpkm	MS POP	Scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Transport	Passenger train	Bpkm	MS POP	Scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Transport	Passenger train – metro/tram	Bpkm	MS POP	Scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe		Population	mIn	Projection	Scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe		CO2 / energy policy measures / targets			Scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe		Technology cost projections	Meur/GW or Meur/PJ		Scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe		Renewable potentials	GW or PJ		Scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe		Cost of Capital	%		Scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe		Transport modi	change		Scenario	EU MS
7	CALLIOPE		CO2 / energy policy measures / targets			Scenario	EU MS
8	ELDEST	Power sector	CO2 / energy policy measures / targets			Scenario	EU MS
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Free emissions allowances (ETS/CO2 tax)	Mt		Scenario	EU
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	CO2 / energy policy measures / targets			Scenario	NL

The aim of the AMIGDALA integrated model suite is to project transformative pathways which lead the European process industry to a climate-neutral, more circular, and yet competitive future. It consists of nine individual models that are soft linked to allow coordinated operation. This setup enables the integration of the Economy, Energy, Environment, and Materials domains across a wide geographical scope, from the global level, with a focus on the EU and its member states, down to the local level of a single industrial cluster. In addition, this integrated approach offers the opportunity to combine different modelling time-resolutions providing more detail to the local level.

Different technological CO₂ mitigation solution routes exist to make a transformation to a CO₂ neutral industry. These relate to different domains such as energy, circularity and CO₂ capture, storage and use. These types of options can be related to distinct parts of the value chain. Hence, these types of solution routes can be related to the five dimensions and are listed accordingly in Table 9.

It is the aim of AMIGDALA to cover all these types of solution routes in the integrated model suite. For that reason, different types of models are needed, e.g. macro-economic, energy system, land-use, dynamic mass flow and stock and techno-economic models. These are indicated in the right column of Table 9.

The set of important model output parameters will be discussed in the section on the module post-processing of raw model output. We conclude this section by describing the inputs and outputs of the module integrated model suite. See Table 10.

Table 9. Overview of types of CO2 mitigation solution routes to cover, related to the five dimensions.

Dimension	#	Solution route	Relevant model
(1) energy demand and use and energy efficiency	1	energy efficiency	TIAM-ECN, TIMES-Europe, CALLIOPE, CIMS
	2	heat electrification (low CO2)	
	3	process electrification (low CO2)	
	4	(green) hydrogen	
(2) emissions including process emissions	5	CCS (and all other options in this table)	CIMS
(5) possibility of replacing fossil carbon in materials by more sustainable streams (e.g., recycled carbon from industrial emissions, from waste, sourced from sustainable biomass or directly from the atmosphere)	6	CCU (incl DAC)	GLOBIOM
	7	biomass	PRISM
(3) use of raw materials, chemicals, and water (e.g., via increasing the use of circular approaches and material substitution, also in view of ensuring affordability of industrial products)	8	recycling (close the loop)	
(4) production of consumer goods / equipment / construction products (e.g., looking at sustainability of products and embedded carbon – a preliminary approach only)	9	refuse and reduce (narrow the loop)	Process industry TIMES-Europe (raw minerals not implemented), TIAM-ECN, (GLOBIOM bio), Recycling & chemicals / water CITS, PRISM, CALLIOPE, CIMS
	10	material substitution	
	11	lifetime extension (slow the loop)	EXIOMOD, CITS

Table 10: Inputs and outputs of Module Integrated model suite

	Module Integrated model suite
Inputs & data requirements	<u>Model data input requirements overview.xlsx</u> from module Background and foreground scenarios and narratives
Outputs	<u>MIGDALA sectors and carriers.xlsx</u> to module post-processing of raw material output

3.6. Post-processing of raw model output

In order to derive the indicators, which are most relevant for the stakeholders, decision makers from governments and industries, the raw model outputs need to be filtered and post-processed. In Table 11 it is detailed which indicators are foreseen from a model perspective. Here, we make a distinction between metrics used for WP2 PoC (bold font), metrics available in WP3 (normal font) and metrics probably not possible within the AMIGDALA models (italic grey font). These indicators supplied from the models covering all relevant five dimensions have to be aligned with the stakeholder needs.

Table 11. Overview of Model outputs for the five dimensions (bold=for WP2 PoC; normal=in WP3; red italic=probably not possible within AMIGDALA).

<i>Dimension</i>	<i>Key model outputs/metrics</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Additional model outputs/metrics</i>	<i>Unit</i>
(1) energy demand and use and energy efficiency	Process industry (or process) energy demand (Final + Primary)	PJ	By energy carrier	
<i>Process oriented</i>	Specific process sector energy demand	PJ/Mt	Product group volume	Mt
	Technology (system) costs	€/t	Renewable share	%
	Energy carrier prices	€/GJ	Biomass for energy	PJ
	<i>Material production costs / prices</i>	€/t	Electrification (share of total final energy)	%
(2) emissions including process emissions	Process industry CO2-eq. emissions (process, energy, upstream, downstream)	kton	by GHG	kton
<i>Process + also scope 3 up- and downstream = life cycle</i>	Specific process sector CO2-eq. emissions	t/t		
	CO2 price	€/t	CO2 price ETS1, ETS2	€/t
(3) use of raw materials, chemicals, and water	Process industry raw material input	kton	By raw material	
<i>Material input focus</i>	Specific process sector raw material input	t/t	By virgin, recycled, renewable	
	<i>Chemicals and water</i>	kton		
(4) production of consumer goods / equipment / construction products	Manufacturing production value (real & volume)	M€		
<i>Downstream Product manufacturing, including all circular R-strategies</i>	Product group material demand	kton	By material	
	Specific product group material demand	t/t	By material	
	Import of product group material	kton	By material	
	<i>Employment / Jobs</i>	nr or €		
(5) possibility of replacing fossil carbon in materials by more sustainable streams	(Fossil) Carbon based feedstock consumption - Chemical industry (for PoC double with point 3)	kton	Naphtha, Natural gas, LPG, refinery gas, ethane, other oil products	
<i>Renewable / circular feedstock - focus on carbon</i>	By fossil, recycled, biobased, air	kton		

For the PoC, a more detailed design of KPIs has been made in Table 12. Here, for each indicator the aggregation level and the model are depicted.

Table 12. Overview of metrics for the PoC, in relation to aggregation level and model.

<u>Dimension</u>	<u>Key model outputs/metrics</u>	<u>Unit</u>	<u>Aggregation (By scenario)</u>	<u>Related model</u>
(1) energy demand and use and energy efficiency <i>Process oriented</i>	Process industry (or process) energy demand (Final + Primary), by energy carrier	PJ	EU v ROW; EU and EU MS; Region or site	TIAM-ECN; TIMES-Europe; CIMS
(2) emissions including process emissions <i>Process + also scope 3 up- and downstream? = life cycle</i>	Process industry CO2-eq. emissions (process, energy, upstream, downstream)	kton	EU v ROW; EU and EU MS; Region or site	Process + upstream GHG TIAM-ECN, GLOBIOM; TIMES-Europe, downstream emissions CITS, PRISM; CIMS, CALLIOPE
	CO2 price	€/t	EU v ROW; EU; Region or site	TIAM-ECN; TIMES-Europe; CALLIOPE, CIMS
(3) use of raw materials, chemicals, and water <i>Material input focus</i>	Process industry raw material input, see point (5)	kton	EU v ROW; EU and EU MS; Region or site	Process industry TIAM-ECN, (GLOBIOM bio); TIMES-Europe (raw minerals not implemented), Recycling & chemicals / water CITS, PRISM, CALLIOPE, CIMS
(4) production of consumer goods / equipment / construction products <i>Downstream Product manufacturing, including all circular R-strategies</i>	Manufacturing production value (real & volume)	M€	EU v ROW; EU and EU MS; Region or site	EXIOMOD; CIMS
	Product group material demand	kton	EU, EU MS	CITS (demand <> production of TIMES-EUR!)
(5) possibility of replacing fossil carbon in materials by more sustainable streams <i>Renewable / circular feedstock - focus on carbon</i>	(Fossil) Carbon based feedstock consumption - Chemical industry (for PoC double with point 3)	kton	EU v ROW; EU and EU MS; Region or site	TIAM-ECN, GLOBIOM; TIMES-Europe, PRISM; CALLIOPE, CIMS
	By fossil, recycled, biobased, air	kton	EU v ROW; EU and EU MS; Region or site	TIAM-ECN, GLOBIOM; TIMES-Europe, PRISM; CALLIOPE, CIMS

These outputs will go to the Destination pathways and narratives as well as the Data explorer which forwards the KPI's to the Decision logic.

Table 13: Inputs and outputs of Module Post-processing of raw model

3.	Module Post-processing of raw model output
Inputs & data requirements	From each model in the Integrated Model Suite
Outputs	Amigdala sectors and carriers.xlsx

3.7. Destination and pathway narratives

The transition toward climate neutrality is not a single road but a network of possible routes, each shaped by decisions made today. *Destination narratives* describe what a sustainable, resilient, and competitive European industry could look like in the future. These narratives are not abstract ideals but practical depictions of industrial systems that have successfully adapted to new technologies, policies, and market realities.

Pathway narratives, in turn, illustrate the steps required to reach these destinations. They map out critical decisions, investments, and policy shifts, showing how industries can transition from current practices to low-carbon, circular, and energy-efficient models. Each pathway accounts for barriers and accelerators, highlighting how different strategies, whether focused on technological innovation, regulatory support, or market-driven adaptation, shape the journey.

By presenting clear, structured narratives, AMIGDALA helps decision-makers visualize the future they want to achieve and understand the choices needed to get there.

The design of these narratives is guided by four key inputs:

1. **Scenario drivers:** Scenario drivers are the fundamental forces that shape the evolution of industrial systems and influence the feasibility and effectiveness of transformation pathways. In AMIGDALA, scenario drivers are categorized into two main types:
 - **External Drivers:** Factors outside the direct control of stakeholders, such as global economic trends, technological advancements, geopolitical dynamics, and societal behaviour changes. These drivers provide the contextual backdrop for scenario analysis, ensuring that pathways are grounded in realistic external conditions.
 - **Control Levers:** Strategic choices available to decision-makers, including policy interventions, investment incentives, and regulatory frameworks. Control levers are modelled to reflect realistic and actionable options for government and industry stakeholders.
2. **Uncertainty evaluation:** identifying critical uncertainties that influence scenario outcomes helps to manage strategic risks and

ensure that pathways are robust to disruptive events and black swans events. Key critical uncertainties may be assumptions on energy prices, technology costs, and carbon pricing.

3. Model results: The destination and pathway narratives are informed by integrated model results from AMIGDALA's comprehensive suite of domain model. Key results include detailed projections of energy demand, emissions, resource flows, and economic impacts.
4. Benchmarking with existing publications: Benchmarking reveals gaps in existing literature, guiding strategic adjustments and ensuring that AMIGDALA scenarios remain forward-looking and comprehensive.

The key outputs of this module include destination narratives by industry sector and pathway narratives that map out strategic routes to achieve these destinations. These outputs are meticulously crafted to provide actionable insights, guiding decision-makers through the complexities of transitioning to climate-neutral industrial systems.

Table 14 provides an overview of the inputs, data requirements, and outputs for this module.

Table 14: Inputs and outputs of Module Destination and pathway narratives

	Module Destination and pathway narratives
Inputs & data requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scenario drivers • Uncertainty evaluation • Model results, key performance indicators trajectories (technological, economic, and other) • Benchmark with non-AMIGDALA publications, identifying similarities and differences.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Destination by industry sub-sector • Pathway narratives on how to get there.

3.8. Decision logic

Each independent model run is characterised by a set of inputs and outputs as defined in scenarios. These values are used to calculate specific indicators associated to key questions coming from the stakeholders. Indicator values are then aggregated into a global score used for model runs' ranking.

Each KPI indicator is associated both to dimensions of climate neutrality and assessment dimensions. While the five dimensions of climate neutrality are focused on a specific topic, assessment dimensions are broader concepts such as Competitiveness, Resilience and Climate neutrality.

Indicators were selected as the most relevant themes to policymakers and industrial decisions makers. These are referred to as KPIs (Key Performance Indicators). In WPI, interviews were undertaken with policy and industrial decision makers. These interviews aimed at identifying the data required to take decisions furthering (or impeding) Green Deal objectives. These interviews yielded a long list of 29 indicators. This long list was broken down into a short list of 10 identified as KPIs. These KPIs were selected based upon the recurrence of their mentions during interviews across both different populations.

10 "aggregated" KPIs, with a preference for the 2 different profile types

	#	KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATOR (KPI)	
INDUSTRY	1	Energy mix evolution and price	
	2	Availability & cost of technology	
	3	Raw material and feedstock availability and cost	
	4	Demand evolution in Europe and globally + Trade balance	
POLICY	5	Carbon price trajectory	
	6	Industry emission reduction	
	7	Job creation	
	8	Tax revenue + cost to public sector	
	9	Demand evolution in Europe and globally + Trade balance	
	10	Wider environmental impact	

The above is our draft working proposal

Figure 6: Selection of KPIs according to two different user populations.

These KPIs will serve to characterize scenarios and thereafter sort them based upon user preferences. As the filter through which users will be able to select and visualize scenario results, they require numeric and/or graphic interpretations.

KPIs are visualised as sets of specific charts depicting model output's information in the most effective way for the type of information provided. Such charts should help answer the question related to the assessed KPI.

17 indicators for 4 KPIs

#	KPIs	#	Indicators	Representation type
1	Energy mix evolution and price	11	Price for each type of energy vector used over the period	Trajectory
		12	"High/medium/low" appreciation of the trajectory's ambition	Qualitative data
		13	Relative increase to today (% increase from baseline)	Quantitative data
		14	Sankey of use of different energy vectors per sector over time	Sankey
		15	Total energy use (ex: in PJ) split by vector	Quantitative data
2	Availability and cost of technology	21	Marginal Abatement Cost Curve of technologies per sector	MACC
		22	Overall increase costs split between capital and operational costs	Bar chart
3	Raw material and feedstock availability and cost	31	Price trajectory over time (presented with raw material availability)	Trajectory
		32	Relative increase compared to baseline (ex. %) per type of raw material	Bar chart
		33	Share of total raw materials imported vs non-imported	Pie chart
		34	Sankey of raw materials with share of imported & non-imported	Sankey
		35	Sankey of raw material flow per sector	Sankey
4	Demand evolution in Europe and globally + Trade balance	41	Total availability & use of raw materials	Pie chart
		42	Indicator of growth of EU vs RoW	Bar chart
		43	Overall share of EU vs RoW production	Quantitative data
		44	Overall share of EU vs RoW capacity per sector	Pie chart
		45	Bar charts per sector over time (& potentially per country) at EU Level.	Bar chart

The above is our draft working proposal

Figure 7. Selection of indicators for 4 KPIs

20 indicators for 6 KPIs (1/2)

	KPIs	#	Indicators	Representation type
5	Carbon price trajectory	5.1	Carbon price represented as a trajectory	Trajectory
		5.2	"High/medium/low" appreciation of the trajectory's ambition	Qualitative data
6	Industry emission reduction	6.1	Overall emissions variation	Bar chart
		6.2	Emissions per sector over the period	Trajectory
		6.3	Total emission value per year, sector and country	Bar chart
7	Job creation	7.1	Total number of jobs created & destroyed per sector & country	Bar chart
8	Tax revenue + cost to public sector	8.1	Share of taxes taking as a share of production (e.g. with a fixed VAT)	Bar chart
		8.2	Trajectory of taxes vs subsidies for the sector per sector per year	Bar chart
		8.3	Emission reduction for a given sector divided by prior subsidies over time	Quantitative data
		8.4	Representation of the efficiency of public subsidies	MACC
		8.5	Share of taxes taking as a share of production (e.g. with a fixed VAT) represented as a total	Quantitative data
		8.6	Evolution of taxes vs subsidies for the sector as a bar chart per sector per year	Bar chart

The above is our draft working proposal

20 indicators for 6 KPIs (2/2)

	KPIs	#	Indicators	Representation type
9	Demand evolution in Europe and globally + Trade balance	9.1	Demand per sector over time (& potentially per country) at EU Level.	Bar chart
		9.2	Indicator of growth of EU vs RoW.	Quantitative data
		9.3	Demand per sector/country over the period of EU/RoW production share	Bar chart
		9.4	Share of demand met within the EU vs RoW.	Pie chart
10	Wider environmental impact	10.1	Expected biodiversity impact according to the foreground scenario	Qualitative data
		10.2	Material flows per sector over time	Sankey
		10.3	Share of circular material per sector	Pie chart
		10.4	Indicator to be developed	TBD

The above is our draft working proposal

Figure 8. Selection of indicators for 6 KPIs

To move from model data to KPIs to the final score, a sequence of hierarchical aggregations takes place in order to make the results easily assessable by the user and to allow prioritization as reported in Figure 9.

Figure 9: hierarchical organization of information.

In order to aggregate model outputs into KPIs, specific transformation functions take place which provide insightful information for example by summing different types of energy demands into global energy demand or representing use of a raw material for a specific sector as a percentage of the total.

To further aggregate KPIs towards the final ranking, data needs to be normalised first. In fact, each model output and KPI is associated with diverse types of data, with different units of measure and domains. Specific normalisation functions are tailored to the data types and domains they are applied to, but all of them share the same codomain in the $[0, 1]$ range. After normalisation is applied, it is then possible to aggregate data using any Multi Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) formula as all data pertains to the same $[0, 1]$ domain representing their “utility” given the problem to be faced.

To take user preferences into account, parametric aggregation functions are used which consider user’s preferences as weights. Preferences are acquired from the user as importance scores associated to the ten KPIs. In future releases, predefined preference profiles will be proposed to the user to simplify the scoring process.

Users can filter out model runs to focus only on results meeting their expectations by utilising control levers. Each control lever is associated with models’ inputs and outputs and is characterised by a limited number of classes (e.g. Feedstock supply: increase, maintain, decrease).

Each class identifies a range of valid values for the associated model's input and outputs allowing for filtering. Control levers configurations are associated with scenarios so that, selecting a scenario automatically entails a specific class for each control lever which the user can decide to further modify.

The presented decision logic structure needs several inputs from the other modules as reported below. All these data are collected in tables as reported in detail in chapter 5.

Table 15: Inputs and outputs of Module Decision Logic

Module Decision Logic	
Inputs & data requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scenarios. - Control levers and their classes. - Association between scenarios and control levers classes. - KPIs and related questions, model data, preferred charts. - Assessment dimensions and dimensions of climate neutrality associated with KPIs.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Excel PoC prototype logic

3.9. Decision dashboard

The decision logic presented in the previous section is implemented in the Decision dashboard. Aim of the dashboard is to support stakeholders and legislators in their decisions. It provides them with a tool that allows the data to be shown in a clear and understandable way.

The AMIGDALA framework's diverse models, focusing on different heterogeneous aspects will generate a large volume of data, potentially creating a difficult-to-navigate repository. Therefore, it is essential that this data is elaborated and presented in an organized way, to allow the decision makers to focus on the results that really matters.

The decision dashboard is the tool that decision makers will approach first. It acts as a funnel, taking all the raw data from the data repository, filtering it, and presenting it in a way that better emphasize the actual meaning of the results.

The first prototype of such tool is developed in WP2 as a Proof of concept as a Microsoft Excel file. The prototype presents an initial

selection of scenarios, control levers and user preferences used to filter and prioritise results from the models.

Model results are integrated into different KPIs used to answer specific questions. The tool displays statistical descriptors of KPIs as well as detailed results charts.

Table 16: Inputs and outputs of Module Decision dashboard.

	Module Decision dashboard
Inputs & data requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scenarios names - Control levers names and classes - KPIs names and charts.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Excel PoC prototype.

4. Interactions between the modules

This chapter discusses the relationships between the modules discussed in chapter 3, focusing on the exchange of data from one module to another. The aim of this description is to formalise which data will be exchanged between modules and to establish a shared understanding of its meaning - covering definitions, granularity, and units.

4.1. Data flow between repository, models, and public interfaces

Data management is essential for the successful interaction between the models, the integration of the scenario levers and lastly, the ability to retrieve and display data, and derive interpretations for the overarching decision dashboard. The data management process focuses on the harmonization of input data for the models, as well as efficient data exchange and transparency across the whole AMIGDALA framework. This is achieved by leveraging a robust data repository, collecting historical data to contextualise the model outcomes, and putting in place the necessary tools for the exchange, retrieval, and visualisation of data.

All data within the system will be managed in accordance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), ensuring that datasets are properly catalogued, easily accessible to authorized users, and structured in a way that facilitates interoperability across different systems and future use cases.

A scheme of an exemplary data flow is depicted in Figure 10. When a model requires input data, it queries the repository to retrieve the necessary datasets for a specific model run, so that it uses the most current and harmonized information (bottom left black arrow). If necessary, data from the repository is converted to the needs of the model (grey boxes) available. Once the model has run, it makes another call (black arrow on the bottom right) for its results to be saved in the data repository. For this, a conversion of data might also be necessary to fit the repository's data requirements.

Like this, the repository will always be up to date, and its content will be viewable in the data explorer.

Figure 10 Draft of data flow between the models, data repository, data explorer and external parties. The black arrow indicates calls to the data repository. After each model run, it is yet to be discussed, whether a conversion of the raw model output is needed before saving. In any case, however, the data conversion will take place outside of the data explorer.

4.2. Data repository – Scenario building

The scenario building module aims to identify drivers that impact the industrial sector and, from that, design scenarios for the development of most relevant drivers. Three aims reflecting the main scope and ambitions of the AMIGDALA project have been identified:

- Environmental sustainability
- Competitiveness of EU energy intensive industries
- Strategically autonomous European economy

Drivers have to be analysed and rated basing on their relevance and uncertainty for these three dimensions in the future. Some factors can be considered with low uncertainty, while for many others there are several projections' options over the years; in this case, data about uncertainties have to be collected through a mix of scenario options. Population's evolution can be evaluated as certain, with only one trajectory, but drivers like GDP or tertiarization should be projected at least binary (e.g. high/low GDP growth, high/low tertiarization). This kind of data are needed both for "contextual" driver, such as trade balance or more in general geopolitical aspects, and for control levers, being the direct drivers that influence the transformation pathways of industry. Examples of background drivers' variation are in the following table:

Table 17. Background drivers

Driver	Variation(s)
Population	One trajectory (e.g. Eurostat projection)
GDP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high growth • low growth
Geopolitics /trade tariffs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • re-globalization • rival trade blocks

Industry and policy decision makers' needs have been investigated through a set of interviews. The results have been condensed in a list of indicators from which data required for scenario building can come from **Decision logic**. Energy price trajectories for energy vectors over the period, or the demand evolution in Europe and globally could be examples of industry data required for scenario building, as well as trajectory of carbon price or trajectory of emissions per sector could be policy data. In addition to stakeholders' suggestion, other data could be needed to build scenarios, such as population trend over the years, technology cost and evolution.

For the scenario building, historical data have to be collected for the selected drivers, coming from data expertise, as well as the potential evolutions of key data related to the scenarios, such as product demands and GDP. Data collection is a shared responsibility between Scenarios and Data expertise, where scenario can provide guidance for data module.

Source of data can be several, with the following being possible ones:

- IIASA scenario explorer,
- Open Entrance scenarios,
- IPCC Sixth Assessment Report,
- IEA Energy Technology Perspectives 2024,
- Potentia 2024,
- Eurostat

In the following table an example of the interconnections among scenarios and data repository can be found, regarding environmental sustainability's scenarios building. In particular, two main aspects of the environmental sustainability dimension are explored (called sub-dimension), i.e. the climate neutrality and the circular economy. These,

as well as other sub-dimensions identified for competitiveness and strategically autonomous economy, are main scopes and ambitions to be reached in AMIGDALA project.

Table 18. Interconnections between scenarios and data repository.

Scenario building		Data repository
Sub-dimension	Scenario indicator	
Climate neutrality	EU level GHG emission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total production of energy-intensive products to meet EU demand • Energy and materials production efficiency • Energy mix
Circular economy	Share of secondary raw material usage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycling technology costs and capability • Availability of recycled based materials

A simplified system view is offered in Figure 11, which shows the interconnections among the three dimensions of the scenario building (environmental sustainability, competitiveness and strategic economic autonomy) and some of the data needed in the repository for the selected drivers.

Figure 11. Interconnections among environmental sustainability, competitiveness, and strategic economic autonomy.

Finally, data from scenarios have to be integrated into the data repository, in particular the foreground scenarios built for the full model suite by combining backgrounds and a set of control levers. These include an internally consistent datasets related to scenario definition, boundary conditions and a baseline scenario that includes background and foreground elements.

4.3. Data repository – Integrated model suite

As described before, in the final AMIGDALA framework, all data exchange between models within the Integrated Model Suite will be going through the Data repository, herewith allowing for data alignment and validation.

In the Proof of Concept, this is not yet the case since short cuts are taken to exchange data from model to model, as will be described in the chapter on Data exchanges between models. This has to be seen as a trial situation where we set up the data exchanges as it will be implemented later in the Data repository.

In addition, the Integrated Model Suite will receive and send data to the Data repository. The Integrated Model Suite will receive scenario data through the Data repository and will send raw (pathway data) and post-processed (KPI) model outputs to the Data repository. There it will be stored, processed, and analysed as a basis for other modules such as the Data explorer and Decision logic.

4.4. Data repository – Decision logic

The Decision logic module is designed for high-level management of complex, long-term climate change goals. It enables decision-makers to explore various policy pathways by adjusting initial conditions, boundaries, and preferences. The system then ranks these alternatives based on their performance.

This module relies on the Data Repository, which stores inputs and outputs from the Integrated Model Suite. It uses this data for decision-making through two key processes: filtering and aggregation. Filtering selects relevant model runs based on specific inputs and outputs tied to control levers. Aggregation then scores these runs by associating model data with KPIs, visualizing them in charts, and combining them into a ranking score.

Essentially, the Data Repository provides all necessary information about model inputs, outputs, their relationships to control levers, and the resulting aggregated KPI values, enabling the module's decision logic.

4.5. Integrated model suite – Scenario building

The interaction between scenarios and the integrated model suite within the AMIGDALA framework builds upon a bridging approach that connects qualitative scenario building with quantitative systems modelling. Specifically, scenarios illuminate model development needs and pinpoint the inputs required for integrated models. In turn, models inform scenarios about the background and control levers required for accurate modelling. The interaction between the scenario module and the integrated model suite unfolds through a series of iterative feedback loops:

1. Scenario initialization: boundary conditions, control levers, and key performance indicators are defined in this step.
2. Model parameterization: scenarios are translated into specific model parameters to tailor the suite to the contextual needs of each scenario.
3. Integrated model execution: the suite simulates cost-effective pathways to climate neutrality under the constraints and conditions set by the scenarios.

4. Feedback and adaptation: model outputs are evaluated against scenario expectations. Discrepancies or emerging trends are then fed back into the scenario module, refining the scenarios to reflect evolving realities. This cycle repeats, enhancing accuracy with each iteration. This refinement process yields a set of storylines that map out potential pathways to climate neutrality. See Figure 12.

Figure 12. Bridging process between the integrated modelling suite and scenarios module

Particularly step 2 will be crucial in AMIGDALA, since the scope of the Integrated Model Suite is unprecedentedly large, covering macro-economy, energy systems and material systems but also different geographical resolutions ranging from world regions to EU Member States and local regions. Starting from available scenarios developed in the IPCC community on economy, energy and climate in world regions, the material system and EU member States and more local aspects are lacking. This means that scenario narratives have to be extended to materials and circularity and detailed to Member States and subsequently parametrized for the models. Examples of these are:

- Demands for products and materials, related to circular economy policies and consistent with global economy, energy, and climate scenarios.
- Price developments of materials, consistent with the energy price projections.

In the next step 3, iterative model runs have to lay the basis for a consistent scenario parametrization for each model at each domain and resolution.

As this is a rather intense process, the data flow between the modules Background and foreground scenarios and narratives and Integrated model suite is not only made through the Data repository (which is the formal way once scenarios have been established) but also directly between the modules (indicated by a dashed arrow in Figure 3).

4.6. Integrated model suite – Decision logic

The decision logic module operates independently of the integrated model suite. All required data flows through the data repository. The model suite runs separately on desktop computers, and its inputs and outputs are then stored in the repository. The decision logic module accesses this stored data via APIs.

Figure 13. Two public interfaces of AMIGDALA: Decision dashboard and Data explorer.

4.7. Public interface Data explorer

The data explorer is a central tool connecting scenarios, model outputs, and decision dashboard, and ensuring model integration through the harmonization of input data.

In the first step, its availability will be restricted to project partners. This is to ensure that before making it accessible to the public, it can be tested thoroughly in regard to anything related to the proof-of-concept.

This includes anything from the initial setup, such as user access and defining the variables and regions to be displayed, to the way how data can be uploaded. Apart from the various scenarios and model runs, historic data on the five dimensions will also be included in the data explorer. Lastly, the graphical visualisation of historic data is one of the major goals for this work package.

As the data explorer will be also available externally, it is also an important public tool providing an insider's look into the details of the AMIGDALA results. This public interface is meant for users wanting to dive into the raw data behind the indicators and KPIs.

The interface design is the standard design from IIASAs Scenario Services (Figure 14). Selecting variables, regional scope and specific scenarios will allow to view the raw data in form of graphs, tables, or diagrams.

Figure 14. Screenshot of the data explorer user interface.

4.8. Public interface Decision Dashboard

The Decision dashboard is the main public graphical user interface of the project. It is meant to be user friendly and to provide guidance and easy to understand advice to the user.

The Decision dashboard allows users to filter out model runs results so to focus only on data that matters to them. It also allows to rank the obtained results according to important KPIs as well as by assessment dimensions and dimensions of climate neutrality to help users clearly understand the implications of their choices. The design of the interface (Figure 15) is based on the selection of simple statements and classes

about control levers and preferences. The user can rapidly set up the dashboard to reflect their vision and navigate through insightful dynamic charts which can properly highlight causes and trajectories for the obtained results.

Figure 15: Decision dashboard user interface.

4.9. Public interface Destination and pathway narratives

Destination and pathway narratives describe the future state of European industry under each scenario (the destination) and the strategic sequence of decisions and developments required to reach it (the pathway). These narratives translate model outcomes into insights relevant for policymakers and industry actors. These narratives also help users contextualise and interpret the results from the Decision Dashboard.

One option is to publish the narratives on the AMIGDALA project website (<https://amigdalaproject.eu>) using three image links per scenario. One link directs to a detailed narrative report (PDF), another to a summary version highlighting key actions (PDF), and a third to the underlying data used to construct the scenario.

5. Data exchanges between models

This chapter discusses the relationships between the models, focusing on the exchange of data between models. The aim of this description is to formalise which data will be exchanged between models and to establish a shared understanding of its meaning - covering definitions, granularity, and units.

5.1. Model linking and running

In the AMIGDALA framework, the integrated model suite is receiving input on data and scenarios to produce pathways for decision analysis, see Figure 16. In the AMIGDALA soft-linking approach the global models: EXIOMOD, TIAM-ECN and GLOBIOM provide the global context for the developments in Europe. These are projected by the models TIMES-Europe, CITS and PRISM. Similarly, the European-level models make sure that the projections on local level (provided by Calliope, CIMS and ELDEST models) are embedded in a coherent European context.

The arrows indicate the linkages made between the different models (dashed arrows are not yet established in the Proof of Concept). The original idea was to run simulation models (left part of scheme) to provide input on constraints for which optimization models could identify cost-effective techno-economic pathways (models on the right part of the scheme). However, the global macro-economic model EXIOMOD needs 'economic shocks' as input for the economy to respond to. These inputs need to be at world region level but also at EU Member State level (since this version of EXIOMOD also details EU MS). For this reason, both the global energy system model TIAM-ECN and the EU MS energy system model TIMES-Europe has to run first to provide EXIOMOD with the energy transition input to 'shock' the economy. After that, the global picture can be completed with GLOBIOM, followed by the EU level model train starting with the stock-flow simulation model CITS, the plastic recycling optimization model PRISM and the energy system optimization model TIMES-Europe. Within TIMES Europe, global information on biomass, fossil and renewable energy availability and prices and EU MS data on product and material circularity and demand as well as recycling potentials are integrated and optimized with respect to climate policy goals.

At local level, TIMES-Europe energy availability and pricing is used in Calliope to assess optimal power infrastructure and in CIMS to calculate cost-optimal CO₂ strategies for the Chemelot site. Calliope provides

pathways to ELDEST to make agent-based analysis of the electricity market. In a later stage, outputs from ELDEST and Calliope can be used to refine CIMS optimization (indicated by the dashed arrows in Figure 16).

Figure 16. Overview of soft-linked models within the integrated model suite within the framework of AMIGDALA, where the numbers indicate the order or model running.

For the proof-of-concept (PoC) we have chosen to limit the number of model iterations/feedback loops, since connecting and aligning the models as described above will reach the AMIGDALA goals on inclusion of materials and circularity, detailing all process industry sectors, alignment of scenarios and different types of models and combining global, EU, MS and local level (see D1.1 Decision framework & integrated

model architecture design). Furthermore, soft linking has been chosen for practical reasons since the 9 models have different owners and run on different servers with different software. For the PoC, it is estimated that the first serial runs of 4 scenarios of the integrated model suite of 9 models will take 2 working weeks (on average about 1 day per model).

As described before, we will follow largely a linear linking chain which starts at global level, continues to European level to finalize at local level. The only exception will be TIMES-Europe which performs an extra run at the start of the sequence (step 1') to provide necessary input to EXIOMOD (more details below). This way-of-working is summarized in Figure 17.

Figure 17. Overview of scenario and model interconnections used for the linear model runs in the PoC (dashed arrows are not implemented yet).

The arrows in this scheme indicate the input needed from either scenario or other model(s). Next to scenario alignment of models, this serial linking and running of models leads to highly interdependent models at each geographical scale but also between scales, herewith aiming for more complete and consistent results.

5.2. Data exchange tables

Following the linkages described in the previous section, data inputs are described for each model separately. Data inputs can be either scenario data or outputs from other models. These are listed in an Excel file named “Model data input requirements overview.xlsx”. The scenario inputs were presented per model in Table 8. In Table 19, the inputs from other models are presented for each model. In this data exchange table, the different inputs are defined for each model in terms of sector, service / energy or material demand and unit. But also it is specified what the driver of the parameter is and the geographical resolution (the years and the time resolution are not presented here for reasons of readability). It immediately becomes clear from Table 19 that the geographical resolution is different for models at different geographical

scales. This is also true for model years and time slice resolution (not presented in the table). This means that in almost all cases some data conversion is needed. Also, it is clear that there is a high level of model integration. This means that models are (1) aligned with each other on these model parameters and (2) models can respond to changes over time.

Table 19. Data exchange table for each model, showing inputs from other models in terms of sector, unit and geographical resolution.

St	Model	Demand / supply	Service / energy / material demand or other	Unit	Driver in AMIGDALA	Coming from	Geographical resolution
2	EXIOMOD	Electricity production	Electricity by coal	share (%)	Electricity mix	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD	Electricity production	electricity by gas	share (%)	Electricity mix	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD	Electricity production	Electricity by nuclear	share (%)	Electricity mix	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD	Electricity production	Electricity by hydro	share (%)	Electricity mix	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD	Electricity production	Electricity by wind	share (%)	Electricity mix	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD	Electricity production	Electricity by wind	share (%)	Electricity mix	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD	Electricity production	Electricity by petroleum	share (%)	Electricity mix	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD	Electricity production	Electricity by biomass and waste	share (%)	Electricity mix	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD	Electricity production	Electricity by solar photovoltaic	share (%)	Electricity mix	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD	Electricity production	Electricity by geothermal	share (%)	Electricity mix	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD	Electricity production	Electricity nec	share (%)	Electricity mix	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD	Manufacturing sectors	Energy demand/ energy efficiency	Annual % change	Physical energy use of sectors	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD	Service sectors	Energy demand/ energy efficiency	Annual % change	Physical energy use of sectors	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD	Transport sectors	Energy demand/ energy efficiency	Annual % change	Physical energy use of sectors	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD	Households	Energy demand/ energy efficiency	Annual % change	Physical energy use of sectors	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD	All sectors and household	Fuel prices	index	Fuel prices	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD	All sectors and household	CO2 price	index	Price	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
2	EXIOMOD	All sectors	Capital costs per sector	index	Learning rate of capital (so that	TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN	7 world regions + EU MS
3	GLOBIOM	Agriculture	Food	1000 t DM /yr	Country level POP/GDP	EXIOMOD / scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
3	GLOBIOM	Agriculture	Feed	1000 t DM /yr	Country level POP/GDP	EXIOMOD / scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
3	GLOBIOM	Agriculture	Livestock	1000 t DM /yr	Country level POP/GDP	EXIOMOD / scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
3	GLOBIOM	Agriculture	Other	1000 t DM /yr	Country level POP/GDP	EXIOMOD / scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
3	GLOBIOM	Forestry	Industrial roundwood	1000 m ³ /yr	Country level POP/GDP	EXIOMOD / scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
3	GLOBIOM	Forestry	Fuelwood	1000 m ³ /yr	Country level POP/GDP	EXIOMOD / scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
3	GLOBIOM	Forestry	Residues	1000 m ³ /yr	Country level POP/GDP	EXIOMOD / scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
3	GLOBIOM	Bioenergy	1st generation	EJ/yr		TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN / scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
3	GLOBIOM	Bioenergy	Energy crops	EJ/yr		TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN / scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
3	GLOBIOM	Bioenergy	Fuelwood	EJ/yr		TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN / scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
3	GLOBIOM	Bioenergy	Residues	EJ/yr		TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN / scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
3	GLOBIOM	Bioenergy	Other	EJ/yr		TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN / scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
3	GLOBIOM		GDP	Euro	Projection	EXIOMOD / scenario	58 world regions; gridded supply
3	GLOBIOM		GHG price			EXIOMOD / TIMES-Europe / TIAM-ECN /	58 world regions; gridded supply
4	CITS	Packaging	Plastic product demand	Mt or % growth	Projection	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
4	CITS	Building & Construct	Plastic product demand	Mt or % growth	Projection	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
4	CITS	Transportation auto	Plastic product demand	Mt or % growth	Projection	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
4	CITS	Transport other (avi	Plastic product demand	Mt or % growth	Projection	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
4	CITS	Electrical & Electroni	Plastic product demand	Mt or % growth	Projection	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
4	CITS	Electrical & Electroni	Plastic product demand	Mt or % growth	Projection	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
4	CITS	Textiles clothing	Plastic product demand	Mt or % growth	Projection	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
4	CITS	Textiles other	Plastic product demand	Mt or % growth	Projection	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
4	CITS	Agriculture	Plastic product demand	Mt or % growth	Projection	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
4	CITS	Houseware, Leisure	Plastic product demand	Mt or % growth	Projection	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
4	CITS	"Other" sectors	Plastic product demand	Mt or % growth	Projection	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
4	CITS		GDP	Euro	Projection	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
4	CITS		Electricity CO2 eq. emission factor	kg CO2 eq./ kWh	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
4	CITS		Steam / heat for industrial processes CO2 eq. er	kg CO2 eq./ MJ	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
4	CITS		Hydrogen CO2 eq. emission factor	kg CO2 eq./ MJ	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
4	CITS		Oil CO2 eq. emission factor	kg CO2 eq./ tonne	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
4	CITS		Gas CO2 eq. emission factor	kg CO2 eq./ tonne	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
4	CITS		Biomass CO2 eq. emission factor	kg CO2 eq./ tonne	Projection	GLOBIOM/ TIMES-Europe	EU MS
5	PRISM	Waste generation	Plastic waste by polymer collected mixed	Mt	Projection	CITS	EU MS
5	PRISM	Waste generation	Plastic waste by polymer collected separately	Mt	Projection	CITS	EU MS
5	PRISM		Electricity CO2 eq. emission factor	kg CO2 eq./ kWh	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
5	PRISM		Steam / heat for industrial processes CO2 eq. er	kg CO2 eq./ MJ	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
5	PRISM		Hydrogen CO2 eq. emission factor	kg CO2 eq./ MJ	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
5	PRISM		Oil CO2 eq. emission factor	kg CO2 eq./ tonne	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
5	PRISM		Gas CO2 eq. emission factor	kg CO2 eq./ tonne	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
5	PRISM		Biomass CO2 eq. emission factor	kg CO2 eq./ tonne	Projection	GLOBIOM/ TIMES-Europe	EU MS
5	PRISM		Electricity prices	Euro/ kWh	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
5	PRISM		Steam / heat for industrial processes prices	Euro/ MJ	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
5	PRISM		Hydrogen prices	Euro/ MJ	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
5	PRISM		Oil prices	Euro/ tonne	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
5	PRISM		Gas prices	Euro/ tonne	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
5	PRISM		Biomass prices	Euro/ tonne	Projection	GLOBIOM/ TIMES-Europe	EU MS
5	PRISM		Ethylene prices	Euro/ tonne	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
5	PRISM		CO2 - ETS1 prices	Euro/ tonne	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
5	PRISM		Primary plastics prices	Euro/ tonne	Projection	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
5	PRISM		Labour costs	Euro / FTE	Projection	EXIOMOD / scenario	

Table 19 continued. Data exchange table for each model, showing inputs from other models in terms of sector, unit and geographical resolution.

St	Model	Demand/ supply	Service / energy / material demand or other	Unit	Driver in AMIGDALA	Coming from	Geographical resolution
6	TIMES-Europe	Commercial	Floor space	m2	MS wages SRV sector	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Commercial	Ventilation & others	PJ	MS wages SRV sector	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Agriculture	Total energy demand	PJ	MS AGR GDP projection	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Transport	Freight Transport – LCV	Btkm	MS GDP	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Transport	Freight Transport – HDV	Btkm	Projection of intra-EU trade x PJ	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Transport	Passenger train – high speed	Bpkm	MS GDP	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Transport	Freight train	Btkm	Projection of intra-EU trade x PJ	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Transport	Passenger aviation – Domestic	Bpkm	MS GDP	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Transport	Passenger aviation – IntraEU / ExtraEU	Bpkm	EU GDP	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Transport	Freight aviation – IntraEU / ExtraEU	Btkm	Projection of international trade	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Transport	Navigation	Btkm	Projection of intra-EU trade x PJ	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Transport	International marine bunkers	Btkm	Projection of international trade	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Industry	Iron and Steel	Mt	Sectoral projection	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Industry	Alumina	Mt	Sectoral projection	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Industry	Aluminum	Mt	Sectoral projection	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Industry	Other non-ferrous metals	Mt	Sectoral projection	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Industry	Cement	Mt	Sectoral projection	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Industry	Glass	Mt	Sectoral projection	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Industry	Ceramics and other non-metallic minerals	Mt	Sectoral projection	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Industry	Paper	Mt	Sectoral projection	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Industry	Pulp	Mt	Sectoral projection	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Industry	Ammonia	Mt	Sectoral projection	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Industry	Chlorine	Mt	Sectoral projection	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Industry	Ethylene	Mt	Sectoral projection	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Industry	Other Chemicals	PJ	Sectoral projection	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Industry	Other Industry Products	PJ	Sectoral projection	EXIOMOD	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	Industry	Plastics	Mt	Sectoral projections	EXIOMOD / CITS / PRISM	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe	GDP		Euro	Projection	EXIOMOD / scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe		Import prices energy commodities	Meur/PJ		TIAM-ECN / scenario	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe		Import prices intermediate products	Meur/Mt		EXIOMOD / TIAM-ECN	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe		Domestic Biomass availability + cost curve	PJ / Meur/PJ		GLOBIOM	EU MS
6	TIMES-Europe		Land use related emissions	kt CO2		GLOBIOM	EU MS
7	CALLIOPE	Industry	Diesel demand aggregated	energy unit (TWh)	Sectoral Projections	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
7	CALLIOPE	Industry	Kerosene demand aggregated	energy unit (TWh)	Sectoral Projections	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
7	CALLIOPE	Industry	Methanol demand aggregated	energy unit (TWh)	Sectoral Projections	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
7	CALLIOPE	Industry	Methane demand aggregated	energy unit (TWh)	Sectoral Projections	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
7	CALLIOPE	Industry	Naphta demand aggregated	energy unit (TWh)	Sectoral Projections	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
7	CALLIOPE	Industry	Electricity demand aggregated	energy unit (TWh)	Sectoral Projections	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
7	CALLIOPE	Industry	Hydrogen demand aggregated	energy unit (TWh)	Sectoral Projections	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
7	CALLIOPE	Industry	CO2 demand aggregated	energy unit (TWh)	Sectoral Projections	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
7	CALLIOPE	Power Sector	Brownfield capacity of power technologies (exis	MW	historical data	TIMES-Europe	EU MS
8	ELDEST	Power sector	Electricity demand	MWh		CALLIOPE	EU MS
8	ELDEST	Power sector	Installed capacities	MW		CALLIOPE	EU MS
8	ELDEST	Power sector	CAPEX power	€/MW		CALLIOPE	
8	ELDEST	Power sector	CAPEX energy (storage)	€/MWh		CALLIOPE	
8	ELDEST	Power sector	O&M fixed	€/MWh*Year		CALLIOPE	
8	ELDEST	Power sector	O&M variable	€/MWh		CALLIOPE	
8	ELDEST	Power sector	Availability factors (PV + Wind)	/		CALLIOPE	EU MS
8	ELDEST	Power sector	Hydro inflow	MWh		CALLIOPE	EU MS
8	ELDEST	Power sector	Technology lifetimes	years		CALLIOPE	
8	ELDEST	Power sector	Max Capacity potentials	MW or MWh		CALLIOPE	EU MS
8	ELDEST	Power sector	ETS/CO2 tax	€/t		CALLIOPE / scenario	
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Ammonia demand	Mt		TIMES-Europe	Demand in NL for chem. Ind.
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Ethylene demand	Mt		CITS	Regional (Chemelot)
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Electricity availability	GWh		TIMES-Europe	availability in NL for Chem. Ind.
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Electricity price	€/GWh		TIMES-Europe	prices in NL
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Natural gas availability	GWh		TIMES-Europe	availability in NL for Chem. Ind.
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Natural gas price	€/GWh		TIMES-Europe	prices in NL
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	(fossil based) naphtha availability	Mt		TIMES-Europe	availability in NL for Chem. Ind.
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	(fossil based) naphtha price	€/t		TIMES-Europe	prices in NL
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Bionaphtha availability	Mt		TIMES-Europe	availability in NL for Chem. Ind.
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Bionaphtha price	€/t		TIMES-Europe	prices in NL
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Biomass (solid, forestry waste) availability	Mt		TIMES-Europe	availability in NL for Chem. Ind.
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Biomass (solid, forestry waste) price	€/t		TIMES-Europe	prices in NL
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Blue hydrogen availability	Mt		CALLIOPE	Regional (Chemelot)
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Blue hydrogen price	€/t		CALLIOPE	prices in NL
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Green hydrogen availability	Mt		TIMES-Europe	availability in NL for Chem. Ind.
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Green hydrogen price	€/t		TIMES-Europe	prices in NL
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Green ammonia availability	Mt		TIMES-Europe	conflicting with the demand?
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Green ammonia price	€/t		TIMES-Europe	prices in NL
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Sorted plastic waste availability	Mt		PRISM	NL
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Sorted plastic waste price	€/t		TIMES-Europe	based on system costs, for NL
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	MSW availability	Mt		TIMES-Europe	availability in NL for Chem. Ind.
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	MSW price	€/t		TIMES-Europe	prices in NL
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	CCS availability	Mt		TIMES-Europe	NL
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	ETS/CO2 tax price	€/t		TIMES-Europe	NL
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	E-naphtha price	€/t		TIMES-Europe	prices in NL
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	E-naphtha availability	Mt		TIMES-Europe	availability in NL for Chem. Ind.
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Methanol price	€/t		TIMES-Europe	prices in NL
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Methanol availability	Mt		TIMES-Europe	availability in NL for Chem. Ind.
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Bio-ethanol price	€/t		TIMES-Europe	prices in NL
9	CIMS	Chemical sector	Bio-ethanol availability	Mt		TIMES-Europe	availability in NL for Chem. Ind.

6. Conclusions and next steps

This chapter offers a concise recap of the main outcomes and insights from the proof-of-concept, highlighting the effectiveness of the soft-linking through data exchange tables. It also outlines the next steps, informed by the lessons learned throughout the proof-of-concept's development.

6.1. Summary of working procedure and data exchange mechanisms

This report has shown a structured approach to integrating diverse computational models, scenarios, and decision-support tools into a cohesive framework. A critical component of this framework is the development and implementation of data exchange tables, which serve as the backbone for ensuring seamless interoperability between models, databases, and decision-making processes.

The data exchange tables define and standardize the inputs, outputs, and dependencies across various modules within the AMIGDALA framework. They facilitate efficient information transfer between models, ensuring:

- Consistency: harmonizing data formats and units across different modelling approaches.
- Traceability: establishing a structured mapping of data flows to enhance transparency.
- Interoperability: enabling smooth integration between models addressing global, European, and local industrial transformations.

6.2. Recommendations for future improvements

Moving forward, the next phases of AMIGDALA will focus on expanding and refining the data exchange mechanism to support large-scale modelling efforts. Key activities include:

- Validating the data exchange process: During the proof-of-concept phase, rigorous stress tests will be conducted to assess the robustness of data linkages and identify potential weaknesses.
- Expansion of model scope: broadening the range of covered sectors, technologies, and commodities to ensure a comprehensive analysis and wider applicability of modelling results.
- Further data research to identify proxies and compensate the gap between model data output and stakeholder expected KPIs and indicators.
- Once proxy approach and data availability are known, review of indicators and stakeholders of indicators and KPIs.
- Finalization of exchange table structures: Refining the definitions, formats, and workflows governing data exchanges to optimize information transfer and usability.

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